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TNA Management Report

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List of Abbreviations

BoD	Board of Directors
DH	Digital Humanities
GA	Grant Agreement
GLAM	Sector that includes Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums
KUL	KU Leuven
M	Month
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
PP(P)	Preparatory Phase (Project)
RI	Research Infrastructure
RS	Research Services
SWOT Analysis	Analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TNA	Transnational Access
WP	Work Package
WU	Work Unit
WU RS/TNA	Work Unit Research Services/TNA

1 Introduction

"Now I remembered that the real world was wide, and that a varied field of hopes and fears, of sensations and excitements, awaited those who had courage to go forth into its expanse, to seek real knowledge of life amidst its perils."

(Charlotte Brontë, Jane Eyre 1847)

The study of religions is one of the few genuinely interdisciplinary academic fields, characterised by a wide range of knowledge loci and a great diversity of data types. These data are subject to very different conditions of transmission, accessibility and interpretation. As a result, **physical, in person access to sources remains essential** for research on religions and cannot be replaced by digital access alone. Sustainable and high quality research in this field therefore depends on the **combination of digital and physical access**, both of which are required to address the multilingual, multi-material and multi-disciplinary nature of religious data.

In addition to providing digital data and tools, key categories of non-digital physical and immaterial sources, practices and forms of expression, as well as additional methodological approaches within the field of research on religions, must be taken into account. Through its Transnational Access programme, RESILIENCE aims to bridge this gap by facilitating structured access to **physical collections, on site expertise and locally embedded knowledge**, while at the same time integrating these with digital resources and services.

The **RESILIENCE Transnational Access programme (TNA)** offers physical and virtual access across national borders to key sources, tools and expertise relevant to the research on religions. Virtual access in this context refers to sources that are available through on-site databases and data repositories or institutional networks but cannot be accessed remotely. TNA supports research stays at a range of European institutions holding unique collections and specialised expertise, including libraries, archives, research centres and other knowledge holding institutions. These collections support research on the historical and contemporary study of religions, major and minor religious traditions, new religious movements, secularisation, non religious worldviews and indigenous religions worldwide.

The aim of TNA is to facilitate efficient and reliable access to sources and services that are otherwise difficult or impossible to consult. Many collections relevant to religious research remain un-digitised, partially catalogued or accessible only under specific conditions. TNA therefore responds directly to the needs of

scholars whose research requires **direct contact with manuscripts, rare books, archival documents, artefacts and other material and immaterial sources**, often held in multiple countries and institutional contexts.

To support excellence driven access to these resources, TNA host institutions provide structured assistance before and during research visits. This includes preparatory support, introduction to collections, guidance on their use and access to local expertise. By reducing administrative and organisational barriers, the programme allows scholars to focus their limited time on research itself and to benefit fully from the expertise available at the host institution.

Beyond access to sources, the TNA programme also strengthens the **networking capacity of researchers in the study of religions**. TNA fellows are connected with relevant experts who can provide tailored scholarly guidance, contextual knowledge and methodological input. In this way, TNA combines access to material resources with access to people and expertise, which is a defining feature of research in this field. The programme is designed to benefit both fellows and host institutions and is embedded in the wider professional network of RESILIENCE.

The pilot TNA activities implemented during the Preparatory Phase (PP) build on the experience of the earlier ReReS project. Between 2018 and 2021, ReReS successfully operated a TNA programme that enabled 87 users from 23 countries to complete research visits, generating a substantial body of scholarly publications and presentations. On the basis of this successful fellowship programme, a non-funded TNA programme focusing on excellence-driven access and networking was developed and piloted during the RESILIENCE PPP.

Within RESILIENCE, TNA has functioned not only as a service but also as a **prototyping activity**, allowing iterative testing and refinement of workflows, procedures and support structures. Each year, TNA activities were planned, implemented and evaluated, taking into account available resources and feedback from both fellows and host institutions. The results of these pilot activities, including achievements, challenges, risks and opportunities, are presented and analysed in this management report, in line with the objectives set out in the Grant Agreement.

1.1 Why the Study of Religions Requires Transnational Access Fellowships

Research on religions presents **specific challenges** that are rarely found in other fields. **Religious traditions refer to the numinous and the sacred**, presupposing realities that transcend the empirical world and remain present in the background of scholarly analysis, even when approached through strictly scientific methods. Sources are transmitted in the **widest possible range of languages and scripts** and include not only written texts but also oral traditions, images, architecture, artefacts, rituals, music and other **material and immaterial forms**.

Access to these diverse sources is often difficult. They are frequently located in religious sites, restricted archives, or repositories that are accessible only through personal contacts and trust based-relationships.¹ At the same time, research on religions is embedded in complex social, political and economic contexts that affect interpretation across time and space. These characteristics make it impossible to conduct research on religions exclusively in the digital environment.

RESILIENCE therefore combines digital infrastructures with physical access to sources and expertise. Transnational Access fellowships allow researchers to move between these spaces and to engage directly with materials, practices and people. In doing so, the **programme also opens access to a third analytical space, the study of non material and experiential dimensions of religion**, which can be approached only through observation, interpretation and contextual engagement. TNA is thus a core instrument for enabling high quality research in the study of religions.

1.2 Key Quantitative Results

This chapter provides an overview of the key quantitative results achieved through the implementation of TNA activities within the RESILIENCE PPP 2022–2026.

During the RESILIENCE PPP 2022–2026,

- 91 applications were submitted,
- 70 applications were accepted,

¹ For this challenge, see also Case Study 1, Chapter 4.6.1, and Case Study 4, Chapter 4.6.4.

- 56 research stays were conducted,
- TNA stays accounted for a total of 822 access days,
- Applicants originated from 24 countries,
- 23 TNA host institutions were engaged,
- 12 publications have been produced to date, with a further 14 publications forthcoming²,
- 20 papers and presentations were delivered at international conferences and workshops,
- 49 completed Fellow Evaluation forms were received and analysed,
- 23 completed Host Evaluation forms were received and analysed,
- A comprehensive set of project documentation (including application forms, evaluation forms, workflows, guidelines, and supporting templates) was developed to support TNA implementation and management.

1.3 Governance, Task Coordination and Stakeholder Involvement

The task is **led by KU Leuven (KUL) in cooperation with the Institute for Applied Informatics Association (INFAI)**, with specific consortium partners contributing to data collection and the drafting of textual inputs such as the Fondazione per le scienze religiose (FSCIRE), École Pratique des Hautes Études (EPHE), University of Warsaw, and Volos). **All consortium partners are involved in the task of piloting and testing** of the TNA management processes and represented within the Work Unit Research Services/ TNA (WU RS/TNA) framework, alongside representatives of TNA Hosts internal and external to the consortium.

The TNA Coordinators at KUL and INFAI hold weekly coordination meetings dedicated to the strategic planning and operational management of the TNA, including the organisation of calls, and the management of both TNA fellows and hosts. In addition, bi-weekly coordination meetings with Work Package 2 (WP2) ensure close alignment on tasks, open questions, and decision-making processes.

² Under the “RESILIENCE TNA Terms and Conditions”, TNA fellows are required to report to RESILIENCE on the outcomes of their TNA stays and to appropriately acknowledge both the support provided by the European Union and their use of RESILIENCE services. In addition, annual surveys are conducted, which demonstrate a steadily increasing number of publications and other research outputs, including conference papers; see Chapters 6.3 and 9.2 for details on publications and other results.

At the consortium level, WU RS/TNA meetings are organised every two months and serve to monitor overall progress, discuss forthcoming steps, address challenges, and provide a forum for clarification and exchange among all involved partners and TNA hosts.

1.4 Structure of the Deliverable

As stated in the Grant Agreement³, this Deliverable D2.12 “TNA – Management Report (TNA-MR)” will “present the results of the pilot TNA activities, evaluating the results, difficulties and potential risks and opportunities”. In line with this objective, the deliverable is structured to **document the development, implementation, management, and evaluation of the Transnational Access programme within RESILIENCE over the period 2022 to 2026**. The report provides a comprehensive account of the pilot TNA activities, presenting results alongside an analysis of experienced difficulties, potential risks, and emerging opportunities.

The report opens with an **Introduction** that outlines the rationale for Transnational Access fellowships in the study of religion, presents key quantitative results, and describes the governance framework, task coordination, and stakeholder involvement underpinning the programme.

Chapter 2 focuses on the **establishment and expansion of the TNA hosting network**. It documents the calls for TNA hosts, the growth of the network over time, the development of in-kind cooperation arrangements, training activities for hosts, and the documentation prototypes produced during the initial phase.

Chapter 3 addresses the **management of the TNA fellowship programme**. It describes the evolution of the call model, the inclusion of GLAM institutes and staff exchanges, the organisation and execution of **five calls for TNA fellowships**, and the workflows applied throughout the application and selection process. The chapter also presents the results of workflow prototyping, collaboration with external infrastructures, and the development of supporting documentation.

Chapter 4 presents the **results of the TNA calls**. It provides an overview of applications and fellowships awarded, analyses results by hosting partner, geographic diversity and gender balance, and documents the

³ Grant Agreement 101079792, RESILIENCE PPP.

workflow for managing TNA visits. The chapter further includes case studies illustrating success factors and challenges, as well as preparatory work towards a dedicated TNA management platform.

In **Chapter 5**, the **strategic evaluation of the TNA programme** is explained. It presents findings from a **mid-term review and SWOT analysis**, identifies **risks and lessons learned**, documents **strategic adjustments**, and reports on **key performance indicators** for Transnational Access.

Chapter 6 focuses on **evaluation and impact**. It analyses **feedback from TNA fellows and hosts**, documents **identified issues and mitigation measures**, and presents outputs resulting from TNA fellowships, including **publications, presentations, and other forms of dissemination**.

Chapter 7 addresses **communication and dissemination activities** related to the TNA programme. It outlines the communication strategy, workflows, channels, materials, and measures used to promote TNA calls and fellowship outcomes, and reports on the overall reach of these activities.

The report concludes with a final **Chapter 8** that **summarises the main findings** and reflects on the overall results and outcomes of the Transnational Access programme.

2 TNA Hosting Network

"For the Gazi Husrev-beg Library in Sarajevo, it is a particular pleasure to be part of this project in which we serve not only as a repository of books and library materials, but also as a network hub, a reliable partner, and a connecting center that links international researchers with other relevant institutions. Our contribution therefore extends far beyond the traditional role of a library."

(TNA Host in Survey, March 2026)

One of the key goals of the preparatory phase for the TNA Programme was to **cultivate a sustainable and diverse network of participating hosting institutes across Europe**, called TNA Hosts. These were integrated into the TNA Hosting Network, which was started in 2022 and is still growing.

2.1 Calls for TNA Hosts: 2022–2023

The first call for TNA Hosts took place in the spring of 2022, amongst RESILIENCE members. A total of seven institutions applied and were accepted as TNA Hosts:

- [FSCIRE](#) / Fondazione per le scienze religiose (Bologna, IT),
- [KU Leuven](#) (BE),
- [Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"](#) (BG),
- [Theological University of Apeldoorn](#) (NL),
- [University of Münster](#) (DE),
- [University of Sarajevo](#) (BIH), and
- [Volos Academy for Theological Studies](#) (GR).

We focused on RESILIENCE member institutes of higher education who were able to commit the in-kind effort needed to fulfil the minimum hosting duties. Each institution signed a memorandum of understanding (valid for the duration of that academic year), accepting the minimum list of duties. These consisted chiefly of access to collections, arranging a work space, connecting TNA Fellows to experts, facilitating the visit, and participating in communication/PR activities. Each TNA Host appointed a TNA Coordinator and TNA Contact Person (sometimes fulfilled by the same person). Hosts were given an information package, which

included a detailed workflow, as well as some tips. Hosts were also given a RESILIENCE TNA webpage listing their available services and assets.

The mandatory in-kind services as determined by RESILIENCE TNA were:

- Free access to collections
- Workplace
- Aid in navigating collections
- Arranging a meet up with at least one on-site expert

Additional in-kind services offered voluntarily by hosts included paid or reduced accommodation, public transportation discounts, airport transfers, hospitality services, access to digital services, free printing, scanning, and copying.

A **second call for TNA Hosts was organized in March/April 2023**. This call was extended to both RESILIENCE members and external institutions, which meant that we had to formalize the application procedure. A **TNA Host Evaluation Board 2023-2024** consisting of WU RS/TNA members, RESILIENCE Board of Director members, and WP2 members was set up to judge all applications and accept new TNA Hosts. New TNA Host candidates were presented by WU members, who wrote a formal report with their recommendations. This report was sent to the board, who then informed the current WU leader of their final decision.

WU members approached possible contenders from within their own networks, leveraging their own regional knowledge and network. We decided against an open call in order to limit the amount of effort required by the WU members, and to be able to exert more control over the quality and shape of the TNA Host Network. To ensure uniformity of information, as well as provide WU members with support, a number of guides and checklists were developed: this includes a guide for approaching new hosts, email templates, meeting checklists, as well as a live FAQ in which ongoing problems could be discussed together. The MOU also received a substantial update, now also outlining the duties of the new TNA Host towards RESILIENCE.

We conducted approximately 40 preliminary negotiations, and received an initial response from 19 institutions. Within the time constraints of the call, this resulted in six new TNA Hosts:

- [Bar-Ilan University](#) (Ramat Gan, IL),
- [Bektashi World Center](#) (Tirana, AL),
- [CIRCSE](#) / Centro Interdisciplinare di Ricerche per la Computerizzazione dei Segni dell'Espressione (Milan, IT),

- [mikado Library](#) (Aachen, DE),
- [New Georgian University](#) (Poti, GE),
- [University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Theology](#) (SI).

Result: With these new TNA hosts, the network of RESILIENCE TNA hosts expanded in 2023 from seven to **thirteen hosts in eleven different countries.**

For the TNA Host Call, see the coverage: [Become a TNA Host for International Scholars - RESILIENCE](#) (26 January 2023); [Six New Hosts for Transnational Access Fellowships - RESILIENCE](#) (10 May 2023)

2.2 Growing the TNA Hosting Network: 2024–2026

In 2024 and 2025 the same active, internal approach was used instead of open calls for TNA Hosts. From 2025 onwards this process was aligned with that of the RESILIENCE Enlargement Committee, where new potential RESILIENCE members were also immediately asked if they wished to become a TNA Host. From 2024 this also included GLAM sector (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) TNA Hosts, most notably the J.A.Comenius Museum in Uherský Brod, Czech Republic.

This resulted in a list of 24 individual TNA hosts:

- FSCIRE (Bologna, IT),
- Archivio Generale Arcivescovile di Bologna, AAB (Bologna, IT),
- Bar-Ilan University (Ramat Gan, IL),
- Bektashi World Center (Tirana, AL),
- Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire de Strasbourg (FR),
- CIRCSE (Milan, IT),
- EPHE (FR),
- Europäische Melanchthon-Akademie Bretten (DE),

- ITSERR Consortium (IT)⁴ with 5 individual hosts in
 - Institute of Information Science and Technologies “Alessandro Faedo” (ISTI-CNR) in Pisa, affiliated to the National Research Council (CNR),
 - Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia (UniMORE),
 - Università di Napoli “l’Orientale” (UniOr),
 - Università degli Studi di Palermo (UniPa),
 - Università di Torino (UniTo),
- J.A. Comenius Museum (Uherský Brod, CZ),
- KUL (BE), including Maurits Sabbe Library and KADOC-KU Leuven,
- (2023-2024:) mikado Library (Aachen, DE)⁵,
- New Georgian University (Poti, GE),
- “Saint Epiphanius” Cultural Academy (Agia Napa, CY),
- Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski” (BG),
- Theological University of Apeldoorn (NL),
- University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Theology (SI),
- University of Münster (DE),
- University of Sarajevo (BIH),
- Volos Academy for Theological Studies (GR).⁶

The final number of TNA hosts at the end of the PPP amounts to 23, following the closure of the mikado Library to the public at the end of 2024.

⁴ ITSERR (Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE) is an interdisciplinary and distributed Research Infrastructure for Religious Studies whose main purpose is to strengthen the RESILIENCE RI in its preparatory phase through the development, testing, and integration of services, tools, training activities, and organisational frameworks. See <https://www.itserr.it/> for more information.

⁵ The mikado Library had to withdraw from the RESILIENCE TNA programme as of 31 December 2024, because it was closed to the public and staff numbers were reduced accordingly. The one outstanding TNA stay could have still been carried out with full access to the library and expert guidance provided as a courtesy of the library, but was not commenced due to scheduling issues on the part of the TNA fellow.

⁶ For descriptions of RESILIENCE TNA Host (active in the 2025 call) with their benefits, collections and expertise, see here: <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/cfa-tna/>

2.3 In-Kind Memorandum of Understanding 2022–2026

Given that there were no financial or legal obligations, **the agreement between RESILIENCE TNA and the TNA Host were framed in the context of a temporary Memorandum of Understanding (MOU).**⁷ The MOU lists the mandatory in-kind services as determined by RESILIENCE TNA:

- free access to collections,
- provide a workplace,
- aid in navigating collections,
- and arranging a meet up with at least one on-site expert.

Additional in-kind services offered voluntarily by hosts included paid or reduced accommodation, public transportation discounts, airport transfers, hospitality services, access to digital services, free printing, scanning, and copying.

The original MOUs created for the first two calls for TNA Hosts were signed for one academic year (2023–2024) and were deliberately designed as a prototype to test and refine the collaboration framework between RESILIENCE and the TNA Hosts; once this model proved effective, a two-year MOU was developed for the remainder of the preparatory phase (2024–2026).

By the end of the PPP, this process resulted in a well-established MOU that is ready to be carried forward into the next implementation phase.

2.4 TNA Host Training Sessions

During the PPP, the WU RS/TNA implemented **balanced and efficient information delivery procedures to support both existing and newly appointed TNA Hosts**. A central element of this approach was the provision of concise and targeted TNA Host Information Sessions, designed to ensure a shared understanding of the TNA framework, roles, and procedures while keeping the time investment for hosts as low and effective as possible.

To welcome and onboard new hosts in particular, the WU organised dedicated online **TNA Host Information Sessions in June 2023, September 2024, and November 2025**. These sessions functioned as

⁷ This version of the MOU will be included in D2.12 TNA Management Report. The MOU included in the annexes is intended for the next phase of RESILIENCE.

structured yet practical training formats, combining strategic orientation with hands-on guidance. They introduced hosts to the overall positioning of the TNA within RESILIENCE, clarified governance and management structures, and explained key workflows related to TNA stays, evaluation processes, and financial procedures. The sessions also contextualised the TNA programme within the broader development phases of RESILIENCE, including future planning beyond the 2022–2026 period.

The information was deliberately delivered in a clear and accessible manner, focusing on what hosts need to know to operate efficiently and confidently within the programme. Each session encouraged interaction and provided space for questions and feedback, allowing hosts to address practical concerns directly and to align expectations with the central TNA management. Following the sessions, newly onboarded hosts received an updated information package, including key reference documents such as the TNA Management Plan, the Host Memorandum of Understanding, the TNA Fellow Grant Agreement, workflows and other guidance materials.

These Host Information Sessions proved to be a concise, supportive, and effective instrument for host engagement. They ensured consistency in information across the academic years, facilitated smooth onboarding of new hosts, and strengthened the shared operational understanding necessary for high-quality implementation of TNA services.

2.5 Documentation Prototypes

The pilots of TNA Host applications resulted in the following documentation prototypes:

- MOU TNA Host RESILIENCE PPP (see Appendix 1)
- TNA Host Admissions Criteria
- Workflow “Becoming a TNA Host”
- TNA Host Evaluation Board
- Guide for approaching new TNA Hosts
- FAQ for approaching new TNA Hosts
- Host Information Package
- Template TNA Host “Tip Sheet”
- Template Recommendation Report for a New TNA Host

3 TNA Fellowship Management

"I am truly happy with my experience and deeply grateful for the opportunity to carry out my research within the RESILIENCE TNA framework. It has been an exceptionally enriching and positive period, both professionally and personally. I sincerely hope that this project will continue and receive further support and funding, so that other scholars may benefit from the same excellent conditions and opportunities."

(TNA Fellow, Evaluation Sheet, October 2025)

This chapter outlines the development and implementation of TNA Fellowship Management during the RESILIENCE preparatory phase (PPP). Coordinated by WU RS/TNA (WP2) at KUL and InfAI, and carried out in close cooperation with WP4 and the TNA Hosts, TNA Fellowship Management aimed to establish reliable, transparent, and scalable procedures for the organisation of TNA calls and the execution of research stays. Building on a dedicated management strategy, workflows, evaluation frameworks, and communication instruments were developed, tested, and continuously refined across five TNA Fellowship Calls between 2022 and 2026.

The chapter addresses the **evolution of the call model (3.1)**, the practical **management of the five calls**, including the **collaboration with the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure - European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EHRI-ERIC) (3.2)**, the **results achieved (3.3)**, the presentation of **selected case studies highlighting both success factors and challenges encountered during implementation (3.4)**, and the **preparatory steps towards a dedicated TNA Management Platform (3.5)**.

3.1 Call Scheduling and Evolution of the Call Model

During the preparatory phase of RESILIENCE, the WU RS/TNA was conceived as a prototype service, requiring a cautious and iterative approach to the scheduling of TNA Fellowship Calls. Accordingly, the programme initially implemented a trial model with **one call per year**, resulting in a single call being launched in both **2022** and **2023**. This approach allowed the consortium to test procedures during call management, evaluation, and host engagement, and develop workflows and documentation.

Following these initial calls, it became evident that a single annual call was insufficient to meet one of the core objectives of the TNA programme: providing **rapid and flexible access** to sources, collections, and expertise. Scholars increasingly require short response times and adaptable planning windows for research stays, which cannot be adequately supported through a once-yearly call cycle. In the long term, the

programme aims to operate through **ongoing calls**, enabling continuous access and positioning RESILIENCE primarily as a facilitator rather than a periodic organiser of access opportunities.

At the preparatory stage, however, the implementation of an ongoing call model would have placed disproportionate demands on administrative resources, particularly prior to the full operationalisation of the TNA Management Platform that is expected in May 2026. Given the successful testing of procedures, the availability of prototype documents, and the growing experience of TNA Hosts, the WU therefore concluded that a **transition to two calls per year** represented a realistic and sustainable interim solution.

This adjusted model was implemented in **2024**, with calls opened from **15 March to 1 May 2024** and **15 October to 1 December 2024**. In **2025**, only one call was conducted in spring (**13 March to 1 May 2025**), as an additional autumn call would have resulted in evaluations and selections extending into early 2026, leaving insufficient time to complete fellowships before the closure of the RESILIENCE preparatory phase in **May 2026**.

The revised call distribution also allowed calls to be shifted away from the summer period, thereby enabling scholars to apply specifically for **summer research stays**, a possibility that had not been viable under the timing of the earlier calls. Overall, this phased and adaptive approach to call scheduling contributed significantly to the maturation of the TNA service and laid the groundwork for more flexible access models in the subsequent implementation phase.

3.1.1 Inclusion of GLAM Institutes

As part of the ongoing evolution of the TNA call model, **TNA hosting was extended in 2023 to institutions beyond the formal RESILIENCE consortium partners**. This expansion explicitly included **GLAM institutions**, as well as **GLAM institutions run by religious communities**, recognising their central role in preserving collections of high relevance for research on religions.

This extension reflected the understanding that many essential sources for the study of religions, including manuscripts, archival records, material and immaterial culture, as well as community-based collections, are held outside academic institutions. Including GLAM institutions therefore significantly broadened the range of materials and expertise accessible for the study of religions through the TNA programme and allowed researchers to engage more directly with non-university custodians of religious heritage.

The decision was discussed and agreed within the **WU RS/TNA framework** and subsequently **endorsed by the RESILIENCE Board of Directors**. It was fully aligned with the **RESILIENCE Consortium Strategy 2023–2026**, which emphasises the creation of synergies at **local, national, and European levels** between public and private institutions, such as universities, research centres, and GLAM organisations, providing and preserving cultural heritage material in the field of the study of religions.

The following GLAM institutions joined the TNA hosting framework:

- [Archivio Generale Arcivescovile di Bologna](#), AAB (Bologna, IT)
- [Bektashi World Center](#) (Tirana, AL)
- [Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire de Strasbourg](#), BnU (FR)
- [J.A. Comenius Museum](#) (Uherský Brod, CZ)
- 2023–2024: [mikado Library](#), (Aachen, DE)⁸
- ["Saint Epiphanius" Cultural Academy](#) (CY)

By integrating GLAM institutions into the TNA hosting model, the programme strengthened its capacity to support interdisciplinary research, foster cooperation across institutional boundaries, and reflect the diverse and distributed landscape of resources relevant to the study of religions.

3.1.2 Inclusion of Staff Exchanges

As part of the further development of the TNA call model, **staff exchanges were introduced as a complementary form of transnational access**, extending the programme beyond researcher-centred fellowships. This evolution was made possible through cooperation with the [ITSERR project](#), the Italian project supporting the development of RESILIENCE, and provided an important opportunity to pilot **funded TNA visits** where direct funding within the core RESILIENCE framework was limited.

Under this cooperation model, funding was restricted to mobility **to or from Italian partner institutions**, but nevertheless enabled the implementation of several strategically relevant exchanges. These staff exchanges focused on **knowledge transfer, methodological alignment, and capacity building**,

⁸ The mikado Library had to withdraw from the RESILIENCE TNA programme as of 31 December 2004 because the library was closed to the public, while still committing to host the remaining TNA fellow visit.

particularly between **Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)** and **GLAM sector TNA hosts**, as well as between partner projects.

A specific instrument introduced in this context was the **TNA Team Exchange**, which allowed staff members to engage in TNA visits. This model was implemented in the **2025 call**, with exchanges from ITSERR to RESILIENCE partners, including visits to **KUL** and **EPHE**. These exchanges facilitated expertise sharing across different professional profiles, such as librarianship, digital humanities, impact assessment, and advanced research support for study of religions.

A particularly illustrative example was the **staff exchange from an Italian partner institution to the TNA Host University of Sarajevo**, implemented in the context of RESILIENCE's Impact activities. This exchange enabled close collaboration between teams working on impact assessment, resulting in **strengthened and more elaborated Impact Plans on both sides**. The experience demonstrated how staff mobility can contribute not only to operational learning, but also to strategic alignment between related research infrastructures.

Overall, the inclusion of staff exchanges marked an important step in the evolution of the TNA call model. It broadened the scope of transnational access from the use of collections alone to the **circulation of expertise, practices, and institutional know-how**, reinforcing collaboration between projects, disciplines, and institutional types. The experiences gained through these pilot exchanges will inform future decisions on integrating staff mobility more systematically into the TNA framework.

For coverage see: [Bridging Impact: A Transnational Access Experience in Sarajevo - RESILIENCE](#) (11 August 2025), [The Value of Both Old and Modern Physical Books will Never be Overestimated - RESILIENCE](#) (10 September 2025), [Exploring AI and the Study of Religion - RESILIENCE](#) (08 October 2025).

3.2 Management of Five Calls for TNA Fellowships 2022–2026

This section outlines the preparation, organisation, and implementation of the **five Transnational Access Fellowship Calls** carried out during the preparatory phase of RESILIENCE. The calls were developed and managed by KUL and INFAL within the Work Unit Research Services framework, in close cooperation with TNA Hosts and consortium partners. Each call was based on clearly defined procedures covering **call design**,

communication, application submission, which were developed in close collaboration and with **significant input from WP4**, and the evaluation and selection process.

Workflows, evaluation criteria, and supporting materials were continuously reviewed and refined to ensure transparency, efficiency, and excellence throughout the call cycles. A strong emphasis was placed on consistent communication, the coordination of independent evaluation boards, and the alignment of selection processes across calls, ensuring both procedural reliability and the high academic quality of the selected TNA fellows.

3.2.1 First Call for Applications for TNA Fellows (Spring 2022)

The first call for TNA Fellows was held in spring 2022 (open May 16 to July 1, 2022). The text for the [call on the website](#) and for the **press release** was developed by WU RS/TNA in collaboration with WP4 and was widely distributed by WP4, the consortium partners and the TNA hosts (see Chapter 7 for further details of communication and dissemination).

A total of 19 applications for five TNA Hosts were received: University of Sarajevo (1), Sofia University (2), VOLOS Academy (2), FSCIRE (7), KUL (7). Eleven of these were accepted: in the period 1 September 2022 – 30 July 2023 these 11 scholars conducted their TNA stays, completing 133 access days.

FSCIRE and KUL together received 14 out of the 19 applications, likely due to their additional substantial benefits: FSCIRE provides paid accommodation for all of its scholars, and KUL provided two scholarships, funding accommodation and travel costs. The quality of the applications was high overall, with only one application denied based on the quality of its proposal.

Related coverage: Kick-off TNA: [RESILIENCE's Transnational Access Program Now Available to the Religious Studies Community - RESILIENCE](#) (16 May 2022); [First Call for Applications RESILIENCE TNA Scholarships - RESILIENCE](#) (16 May 2022); [Current and Next Call for Applications TNA Scholarships - RESILIENCE](#) (11 July 2022).

3.2.2 Second Call for Applications for TNA Fellows (Spring 2023)

The second call for scholars was held in spring 2023 (open March 15 to May 1, 2023). **25 applications for nine hosts were received, 20 of which were accepted**. The increase in both the number of applications, and

number of hosts is great news of course. There is also a large diversity in nationality and country of origin: the 25 applicants were from 15 different countries, and all but one from different institutions.

Three external hosts received applications: CIRCSE, KADOC, and the Bektashi World Headquarters, while four new RESILIENCE TNA hosts also received applications: University of Ljubljana, Bar-Ilan University, Theological University of Apeldoorn (TUA), and the University of Münster. Two scholars affiliated to current TNA Hosts were accepted for other TNA Hosts, a small trend that we would like to encourage. Four scholars re-applied from the previous call (2022). Five scholars also participated in the previous ReReS programme, either via ReReS TNA or via a ReReS school.

See also: [Call for Applications: Transnational Access Fellowships - RESILIENCE](#) (15 May 2023); [RESILIENCE Second Call for Applications TNA Fellowships Closed - RESILIENCE](#) (03 July 2023); [Awarded RESILIENCE TNA Fellowships - RESILIENCE](#).

3.2.3 Third Call for Applications for TNA Fellows (Spring 2024)

The third TNA Call was launched in spring 2024 (15 March to 1 May 2024) and attracted a total of **13 applications across eight TNA Hosts, all of which could be accepted**. One application each was submitted for Fscire, the J. A. Comenius Museum, the mikado Library, the University of Münster, the University of Sarajevo, and the University of Volos, while KUL received four applications and Sofia University three. The uneven distribution of applications may in part be explained by the availability of additional financial incentives offered by some hosts: KUL provided one TNA scholarship per call of up to EUR 500, earmarked exclusively for accommodation and/or travel costs, while Sofia University offered one TNA scholarship of EUR 1,000 in the 2024 and 2025 calls, funded by the National Electronic Research Infrastructure for Bulgarian Medieval Written Heritage.⁹

See: [Call for Applications: Transnational Access Fellowships 2024-2025 - RESILIENCE](#) (15 March 2024); [RESILIENCE Third Call for Applications TNA Fellowships Closed - RESILIENCE](#) (03 May 2024); [Thirteen Applicants Accepted for a Transnational Access Fellowship - RESILIENCE](#) (26 June 2024).

⁹ See for KUL: [Benefits for TNA Users @KU Leuven - RESILIENCE](#), and Uni Sofia: [€ 1000 Funding for a TNA Fellowship in Sofia - RESILIENCE](#).

3.2.4 Forth Call for Applications for TNA Fellows (Autumn 2024)

The fourth TNA Fellowship Call was open from 15 October to 1 December 2024 and formed part of the adjusted call distribution introduced in 2024, which tested the feasibility of running two calls per year in response to scholars' needs for greater flexibility and faster access to sources. At this stage of the programme, **16 research institutions** participated as TNA Hosts, ensuring a broad and diverse range of offerings across disciplines and geographical regions.

A total of **eleven applications** were submitted, of which **ten could be accepted** for research stays at RESILIENCE host institutions. Three fellows were admitted by ITSERR partner institutions (one from ITSERR - Università di Napoli "l'Orientale", and two from ITSERR – University of Turin), two by the J. A. Comenius Museum, two by KUL, two by Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" and one by TUA.

The selected projects covered a variety of research areas and disciplinary perspectives, including historical and philosophical approaches in which religion plays a central role, reflecting the thematic breadth and scholarly diversity supported by the RESILIENCE TNA Programme.

Related coverage: [Call for Applications: Transnational Access Fellowships 2025-2026 - RESILIENCE](#) (15 October 2024); [Attractive Conditions TNA Fellowship at ITSERR Consortium Partners - RESILIENCE](#) (19 October 2024); [Ten Applicants Accepted for a Transnational Access Fellowship - RESILIENCE](#) (15 January 2025).

3.2.5 Fifth Call for Applications for TNA Fellows (Spring 2025)

The fifth TNA Fellowship Call was open from 13 March to 1 May 2025 and marked the final call conducted within the RESILIENCE preparatory phase. The call further expanded the TNA network through the inclusion of two new hosts: the **Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire de Strasbourg (France)** and the **École Pratique des Hautes Études (Paris, France)**, thereby strengthening the programme's coverage in terms of collections, expertise, and geographical representation.

A total of **25 applications** were received in response to the call, reflecting the growing visibility and maturity of the TNA Programme, and also the continued high demand for transnational access to specialised resources within the study of religions. Following evaluation and selection procedures, **15 applications were accepted** for TNA research stays. Of these, one was accepted for the "Saint Epiphanius" Cultural Academy

(Cyprus), four for the École Pratique des Hautes Études (EPHE), two for FSCIRE, one for ITSERR, four for KUL, one for the TUA, and two for the University of Sarajevo. The distribution of accepted applications illustrates both the diversity of host institutions and the diversity of research topics.

See also: [Fifth Call for Applications: Transnational Access Fellowships 2025-2026 - RESILIENCE](#) (13 March 2025); [Attractive Conditions TNA Fellowship at ITSERR Consortium Partners - RESILIENCE](#) (17 March 2025).

3.3 Workflow of the Calls for Applications

Across the five TNA Fellowship Calls conducted during the preparatory phase, TNA Fellows applied via the RESILIENCE TNA website using an online application form. Following the closure of each call, applications were forwarded to the relevant TNA Hosts, where they were assessed by the **on-site TNA Host Coordinators** using the TNA Fellow Evaluation Chart. This expert-led evaluation ensured that the proposed research was justified with regard to the availability of the requested materials, collections, and local expertise, as well as the overall academic quality and feasibility of the project. Based on these assessments, final selection decisions were taken and communicated individually to applicants by the RESILIENCE TNA team, with the coordinators of the selected host institutions informed accordingly.

The overall workflow implemented during the five calls is illustrated in the figure below; for the detailed procedure of evaluation and selection, see [D2.5_TNA Services Management Plan](#), Chapter 3.1.2 Criteria of Excellence.

Figure 1: TNA Fellow Application Workflow

3.4 Results of the Prototyping of TNA Fellow Workflow and Evaluation Procedures

Over the course of the preparatory phase, this workflow was continuously reviewed as a tested prototype with a view to future optimisation. The **academic assessment will continue to be carried out by the TNA coordinators on site**, and the “TNA Fellow Selection Criteria Chart for TNA Hosts” is ideal for this purpose, as it clearly and simply converts the criteria into a scoring system within an Excel spreadsheet.

The development of a dedicated **TNA Management Platform** is intended to automate a substantial part of the management processes, including the forwarding of applications between workflow steps, status updates, and automated communications. This approach preserves expert academic judgement where it is essential, while significantly reducing administrative effort and increasing efficiency in future phases.

3.5 Collaboration with EHRI-ERIC (European Holocaust Research Infrastructure)

In spring **2025**, initial coordination discussions were initiated with **EHRI (European Holocaust Research Infrastructure)-ERIC** with the objective of exploring synergies between the respective Transnational Access Programmes and assessing possibilities for closer cooperation in future phases. These exchanges focused on identifying areas of operational and strategic compatibility, with a view to reducing fragmentation for users and enhancing the overall efficiency of research access services across European research infrastructures.

The dialogue was facilitated by the strong structural and conceptual alignment of the two TNA programmes. Both RESILIENCE and EHRI operate as distributed research infrastructures that offer comparable access services, based on networks of affiliated institutions across Europe that do not necessarily need to be full infrastructure members. In both cases, the programmes emphasise short-term, locally facilitated research stays, typically including direct engagement with on-site experts, and provide lump-sum grants calibrated to national contexts. A shared focus on **physical access to archival and collection-based resources**, particularly those not yet digitised or openly available, further underscored the compatibility of the two approaches.

As a result of these commonalities, the discussions quickly progressed from exploratory exchange to concrete alignment on selected management elements. In particular, convergence was achieved with regard to the structure and content of **Memoranda of Understanding** with future TNA Hosts, the **“Terms and Conditions” applicable to TNA Fellows**, and the **financial framework governing fellowship grants**. This alignment establishes an important foundation for interoperability between the programmes, while allowing each infrastructure to retain its specific thematic focus and governance model.

Looking ahead, a key shared objective is the **integration of the EHRI-EU TNA Programme into the RESILIENCE TNA Management Platform** once fully operational. From a user perspective, this would enable researchers to explore and access TNA Hosts from both infrastructures through a single entry point,

thereby simplifying access pathways and strengthening visibility of available services. From an infrastructure perspective, such integration represents an important step towards scalable, interoperable TNA provision across European research infrastructures in the humanities.

3.6 Documentation Prototypes

The pilots of the TNA Fellow Calls for Applications resulted in the following documentation prototypes:

- TNA Fellow Online Application Portal (offline outside of application periods),
- TNA Fellow Selection Criteria,
- TNA Fellow Selection Criteria Chart for TNA Hosts,
- TNA Letter of Invitation Template,
- TNA Certificates for Fellows,
- TNA Fellow Online Evaluation Form.

4 Results of the TNA Calls

"The distance is nothing when one has motive."

(Jane Austen, *Pride and Prejudice* 1813)

This section presents a consolidated overview of the results of the TNA Calls implemented during the Preparatory Phase. It summarises **application and acceptance figures across all calls (4.1)**, the **distribution of applications and realised research stays per host institution (4.2)**, **analyses factors influencing application patterns (4.2.1)**, and the **geographic and gender diversity of applicants and selected fellows (4.3 and 4.4)**. In addition, it outlines the **visit management workflow** as implemented during the PPP (4.5), and **illustrates programme outcomes and challenges through selected case studies (4.6)** with a summary of **Key Success Factors and Challenges (4.6.4)**, and how these challenges led to the idea of **designing a TNA Management Platform (4.7)**.

Together, these elements provide a comprehensive picture of how the TNA programme functioned in practice and how it supported research in the study of religions across different institutional, geographic, and contextual settings.

4.1 Overview of TNA Calls 2022–2025

This section provides an overview of the five TNA Calls launched between 2022 and 2025. The table below summarises the key figures for each call, including the call dates, number of applications received, number of accepted applications, and number of non-accepted applications.

Across all five calls, a total of **91 applications from 24 countries** were submitted, resulting in the **acceptance of 70 research projects**, reflecting strong demand for the TNA programme and a high level of international engagement.

TNA Calls (Call ID)	Dates Calls	Number of Applications	Number of Accepted Applications	Number of Not Accepted Applications
First TNA Call (2223)	May 16 to July 1, 2022	19	13	6
Second TNA Call (2324)	March 15 to May 1, 2023	25	20	5
Third TNA Call (2425A)	March 15 to May 1, 2024	13	13	0
Forth TNA Call (2425B)	October 15 to December 1, 2024	11	10	1
Fifth TNA Call (2526)	March 13 to May 1, 2025	23	14	9
SUM		91	70	21

Table 1: Results of Five TNA Calls Regarding Applications

4.2 Results per TNA-Providing Partner

The following section presents the **distribution of Transnational Access (TNA) applications and outcomes** across the participating partners. The table below summarises, for each TNA-providing institution, the number of applications received, the number of applications accepted, and the number of TNA stays successfully completed **by April 2026**.

TNA Host	Number of applications received	Number of accepted applicants	Number of completed TNA stays by April 2026
Archivio Generale Arcivescovile di Bologna, AAB (Bologna, IT)	0	0	0
Bar-Ilan University (Ramat Gan, IL)	3	3	0 ¹⁰
Bektashi World Center (Tirana, AL)	1	1	1
Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire de Strasbourg (FR)	1	0	0
CIRCSE (Milan, IT)	1	0	0
École Pratique des Hautes Études (Paris, FR)	5	4	3
FSCIRE (Bologna, IT)	19	14	14
ITSERR Consortium in Modena and Reggio Emilia, Naples, Palermo, Pisa, Turin (IT)	9	4	4 ¹¹

¹⁰ At Bar-Ilan University, the three accepted TNA fellows postponed and subsequently cancelled their research stays as a result of the war in Israel, while the host institution continued to be available for TNA visits.

¹¹ Completed stays: University of Modena and Reggio Emilia: 1, University "L'Orientale" Naples: 1, University of Turin: 2.

TNA Host	Number of applications received	Number of accepted applicants	Number of completed TNA stays by April 2026
J.A. Comenius Museum (Uherský Brod, CZ)	3	3	3
KUL (BE) and KUL-KADOC	22	17	16
mikado Library	1	1	0
New Georgian University (Poti, GE)	0	0	0
"Saint Epiphanos" Cultural Academy (CY)	1	1	1
Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"(BG)	9	8	6
Theological University of Apeldoorn (NL)	3	3	1
University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Theology (SI)	2	2	1
University of Münster (DE)	3	3	1
University of Sarajevo (BIH)	5	3	2
Volos Academy for Theological Studies (GR)	3	3	3
SUM	91	70	56

Table 2: Results of Five TNA Calls per TNA-Providing Partner

By April 2026, **56 TNA research stays had been successfully realised, corresponding to a total of 822 access days** across the participating partner institutions.

4.2.1 Reasons for the Uneven Distribution of Applications

The uneven distribution of applications across TNA-providing partners can be explained by several factors. First, **a number of TNA hosts were not involved from the beginning of the programme**, but joined only in later phases, namely in 2023, 2024, or even as late as 2025; for instance, **BNU and EPHE participated exclusively in the final call**, which naturally limited their overall application numbers.

In addition, **differences in the scope and nature of the programmes offered by the TNA host institutions** naturally influence applicant demand and also vary from call to call. Given the variations in available materials, collections and infrastructure, as well as the diversity of research profiles and thematic focuses, certain host institutions are better suited to the specific research interests of individual applicants than others.

A further contributing factor lies in the **variation in in-kind benefits offered by the hosts**. While some partners, such as **KUL and Sofia University**, provided a limited number of paid scholarships, others offered more comprehensive support, including **free accommodation (FSCIRE)** or **fully funded scholarships (ITSERR)**. These differences are likely to have influenced applicant preferences and demand across partners.

4.3 Geographic Diversity

The 91 TNA fellowship applications were submitted by researchers from **24 countries**, including EU Member States and countries associated with **Horizon Europe**¹²; these countries are **listed in a table and visualised in a map** below.

¹² For the countries associated to Horizon Europe, see [Updates on the association of third countries to Horizon Europe](#), regularly updated by the EC.

	Country	Number of Applications Received
1	Albania	1
2	Algeria	1
3	Belgium	5
4	Bosnia and Herzegovina	3
5	Bulgaria	1
6	Czech Republic	5
7	France	4
8	Georgia	5
9	Germany	12
10	Greece	3
11	Israel	2
12	Italy	17
13	Latvia	3
14	Lithuania	2
15	Netherlands	4
16	Poland	10
17	Portugal	1
18	Romania	2
19	Serbia	2

20	Spain	4
21	Switzerland	1
22	Turkey	1
23	Ukraine	1
24	United Kingdom	1
	SUM	91

Table 3: Geographic distribution of TNA fellowship applications by country

Figure 2: Map showing countries of origin of TNA fellowship applications

4.4 Gender Balance

As outlined in D2.5 TNA Management Plan, Chapter 3.1.3, the TNA evaluation process is designed to promote gender equality and is fully aligned with the [Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans](#). Gender considerations are embedded in the evaluation through the use of “Extra Criterion 1”, which serves both as a tie-breaker for equally ranked proposals and as an incentive for applications that meaningfully integrate gender dimensions into the research design. In the future, gender-equitable evaluation shall be further ensured through the balanced composition of evaluation committees, targeted training of reviewers to address unconscious bias, continuous monitoring and reporting of gender-disaggregated data, and inclusive outreach measures where gender imbalances are identified.

During the PPP, out of the **70 accepted TNA applications, 33 were submitted by female researchers, 35 by male researchers, and 2 were not assigned**, indicating a broadly balanced gender distribution among the selected projects.

4.5 Workflow of the TNA Visit Management

Following the completion of the evaluation phase, **decisions on accepted and rejected applications were finalised by the TNA Hosts**. The outcomes of the selection process were then communicated to all applicants by the TNA Programme Coordinator. Once applicants were informed of the decision, the implementation phase of the TNA visit commenced for the selected fellows.

At this stage, **the local TNA contact person at the host institution** took responsibility for **coordinating the practical arrangements of the research stay in close cooperation with the TNA Fellow**. These arrangements included agreeing on the timing and format of the visit, clarifying access conditions to collections and expertise, and supporting logistical and administrative preparations in accordance with the applicable fellowship guidelines. Throughout this process, coordination between the central TNA management and the local host ensured a smooth transition from selection to access implementation.

While the workflow described above relied on structured manual coordination during the preparatory phase, it was designed with future automation in mind. With the full implementation of the TNA Management Platform, communication of decisions, status changes, and subsequent workflow steps are expected to be handled directly through the digital system. Maintaining an up-to-date overview proved challenging when

TNA Fellows postponed their planned visit dates, in some cases repeatedly. In future, the TNA Management Platform will provide **fellows, hosts, and coordinators with shared access to a single, centralised, and continuously updated data set**, improving transparency and coordination.

The figure below illustrates the visit workflow as it was implemented during the PPP, without the inclusion of the platform-based processes planned for the next phase.

Figure 3: TNA Visit Workflow

4.6 Case Studies, Success Factors and Challenges

This chapter presents four selected case studies that illustrate the practical implementation of the RESILIENCE Transnational Access (TNA) programme. Together, they highlight key **success factors**, such as flexibility, network-based support, and effective mediation, while also addressing **typical challenges** encountered during TNA research stays, including access constraints, crisis situations, and timing or eligibility limitations. The case studies provide concrete examples of how the RESILIENCE TNA framework supports research continuity and academic collaboration under varying and sometimes difficult conditions.

4.6.1 Case Study 1: Managing Access Constraints During a TNA Research Stay

A TNA fellow carried out a short-term research stay at a consortium partner hosting a **culturally and religiously sensitive archival collection**. Although the visit took place as planned, concerns were raised after the stay regarding access to research materials and the overall research experience.

Challenges

The research stay was affected by **administrative and procedural constraints**, including internal approval processes, which limited the time available for in-depth archival research. During the visit, **access to archival materials proved more restricted than the fellow had anticipated**, particularly for documents considered sensitive or confidential.

Following the stay, the fellow requested broader access to archival materials through digitisation and remote delivery. However, these requests were **not compatible with the host institution's archival policies**, which require on-site consultation and restrict off-site dissemination. The resulting mismatch of expectations led to frustration and a complaint addressed to the TNA coordinators.

Actions and Solutions

Upon receiving the complaint, the **TNA coordination team acted as a mediator**, facilitating structured communication between the fellow and the host institution. This process helped clarify institutional constraints and realign expectations. As a pragmatic outcome, selected archival materials were identified

and shared in accordance with host policies, while the fellow was also invited to return for further on-site consultation if required.

Both parties acknowledged the complexity of conducting research in sensitive archival environments and expressed appreciation for the constructive dialogue facilitated through the TNA framework.

Lessons Learned

- Clear and early communication of **archival access conditions and institutional constraints** is essential, particularly when collections are culturally sensitive or subject to special regulations.
- TNA applicants should be encouraged to **define their research needs and expected forms of access as precisely as possible during the application phase**, including any requirements related to digitisation or post-visit access.
- Host institutions benefit from clearly distinguishing between **on-site access, archival research services, and materials that cannot be made available remotely**.
- Active mediation by **TNA coordinators plays a key role** in resolving misunderstandings, managing expectations, and identifying feasible solutions within the framework of the TNA agreements.
- Continuous feedback from both fellows and hosts helps to **refine guidance documents and procedures** for future TNA calls and research stays.

These conclusions were progressively incorporated into the TNA Management Plan, e.g. in the Host Information Package, the Workflow “Becoming a TNA Host”, and in the “Terms and Conditions” Document.

4.6.2 Case Study 2: Ensuring Academic Continuity Through RESILIENCE TNA During Crisis

In the 2023–2024 TNA call, three scholars were selected for research stays at **Bar-Ilan University (Israel)**, planned for autumn 2023. Following the outbreak of the **Israel – Gaza war in October 2023**, escalating security concerns and official travel restrictions made it impossible for the fellows to begin their stays as scheduled, despite the continued readiness of colleagues at Bar-Ilan University to host them.

Challenges

The sudden escalation of the conflict created a **force-majeure situation**, preventing physical mobility and disrupting carefully planned research activities. Beyond the logistical challenges, the situation generated considerable uncertainty for the affected fellows, who faced major constraints on their ability to pursue academic work during a period of broader global instability.

Actions and Solutions

The **RESILIENCE TNA team maintained contact with the fellows**, continuously monitored the situation, and provided guidance based on official travel advice and safety considerations.

One case illustrates how RESILIENCE support can extend beyond access to a single host institution. A TNA fellow from Italy, who temporarily resided in **Paris**, sought to consult a specialist at the **École Pratique des Hautes Études (EPHE)**, a RESILIENCE consortium partner. Although the professor concerned was not formally involved in the TNA scheme, the TNA team facilitated contact in November 2023, enabling a highly productive academic exchange. The fellow later described this interaction as “incredibly beneficial” for her research and highlighted the importance of this support during a period when external events made the continuation of academic work uncertain. She wrote:

“My experience working with Prof. [...] was truly very meaningful for my work, and I’m really grateful that it was possible. It was a particularly difficult time, when everything going on in the world made it feel like research almost had no place. In that context, RESILIENCE was a huge support for me. Even without direct funding, it still offered alternatives, continuity, and a kind of academic stability that I honestly wouldn’t have had otherwise, given the major changes I went through in the middle of the semester. The connections and opportunities RESILIENCE creates can make a real difference for students going through challenging situations like this.” [Quote by the TNA fellow.]

Lessons Learned

- The TNA programme benefits from **flexibility and personalised support mechanisms** when crisis situations disrupt planned research stays.
- The value of a research infrastructure extends beyond physical access, encompassing its **network of expertise and capacity to foster alternative forms of scholarly exchange**.

- Sustained communication between coordinators and fellows is essential to **provide reassurance, guidance, and continuity** under rapidly changing circumstances.
- Even in the absence of direct funding or physical access, **academic support and facilitated connections can play a decisive role** in sustaining research momentum during periods of uncertainty.

4.6.3 Case Study 3: Overcoming Research Barriers Through On-Site Access and Network Support

A researcher based in **Switzerland** undertook a project focused on reconstructing the life of a victim of the **Srebrenica genocide**, requiring access to dispersed archival sources and close engagement with local institutions in **Sarajevo** and **Srebrenica**. Although a period of ineligibility until 2024 at first delayed a formal application, Switzerland's re-association with **Horizon Europe** enabled the researcher to apply successfully in the **2025–2026 TNA call** and to carry out a TNA fellowship at the RESILIENCE TNA host University of Sarajevo.

Challenges

The principal challenge of the project lay in the **difficulty of locating reliable and relevant information** about the individual concerned. Archival holdings in Sarajevo were fragmented across institutions, often only partially catalogued, and difficult to navigate without detailed local knowledge. Desk-based research alone proved insufficient to identify key sources, establish context, or reconstruct biographical details.

A second challenge emerged at a later stage: after completing the TNA stay, the researcher sought to conduct a project in **Greece**, including preparatory work for a student study trip. However, by that point, the final TNA call of the project period had already concluded, making new formal access via the TNA framework impossible.

Actions and Solutions

Through the **TNA stay in Sarajevo**, the researcher benefited from structured access, local academic guidance, and facilitated connections to archives, libraries, and memorial institutions. Crucially, the TNA

fellowship enabled on-site engagement and personal encounters with scholars, archivists, and practitioners, allowing the researcher to trace sources that would have remained inaccessible without institutional backing and local mediation. Field-based research between **Sarajevo and Srebrenica** proved decisive for reconstructing the victim's life story and situating it within its historical and social context.

Following the completion of the TNA stay, the researcher contacted the RESILIENCE team again to request support for building academic connections in **Thessaloniki** ahead of a planned research visit and student excursion. Although a formal TNA application was no longer available, **RESILIENCE facilitated contacts with relevant experts through its network and consortium partners**, enabling continued scholarly exchange and project development.

Lessons Learned

- For complex historical research, particularly in post-conflict contexts, **on-site access combined with local expertise is indispensable** and cannot be replaced by desk-based research alone.
- TNA fellowships can be a **decisive factor in overcoming fragmented archives, access barriers, and informational dead ends**.
- Meaningful academic support does not necessarily end with a funded stay: **network-based facilitation after the closure of calls** can significantly enhance research continuity and impact.
- The added value of RESILIENCE lies in its capacity to provide **both structured access and sustained scholarly support** across different phases of a research project.

4.6.4 Case Study 4: Enabling Inclusive High-Quality Research through Physical Access

This success story illustrates how the TNA research stays at the Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"(BG) highlighted the **indispensable role of physical access to sources** in the study of religions, and demonstrates how RESILIENCE enables inclusive, high-quality scholarship by combining on-site access with carefully designed digital solutions that respect both scholarly and cultural contexts.

Challenges

Rather than addressing a specific problem, this case reflects a **structural constraint inherent to research on religions**: many foundational sources like manuscripts, archival documents, early printed books, and religious artefacts are not fully digitised or cannot be meaningfully studied remotely. In addition, some of the most important collections are subject to historical, geographical, or access-related restrictions that limit who can consult them directly.

Actions and Solutions

Through the TNA stay at the TNA Host, scholars were able to work on-site with a **broad range of collections** held at Sofia University Library and the Zograf Room, the Scientific Archive of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, the Cyrillo-Methodian Research Centre at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Plovdiv Library "Ivan Vazov", the National Library "Ss Cyril and Methodius", the National History Museum; the National Church Museum of History and Archaeology in Sofia, and the Sofia University Centre for Slavo-Byzantine Studies.

A particularly illustrative example is the **Zograf Room at Sofia University Library**, which provides scholarly access to the holdings of the Monastery of St George Zograf on Mount Athos. While the monastery itself preserves a unique and extremely extensive collection of religious heritage, comprising around 1,000 Bulgarian, Greek, Moldavian-Wallachian and other manuscripts; more than 800 medieval and Revival charters and archival documents (Bulgarian, Byzantine, Moldavian-Wallachian, and Ottoman); and hundreds of rare early printed books, its on-site collections are **accessible only to men**.

Through Sofia University as a RESILIENCE partner, these materials are made available **to all scholars, including women**, via the university's digital collections, which can be consulted **on site at the Central University Library**. This solution preserves necessary access conditions while ensuring scholarly inclusiveness and enabling direct engagement with sources that would otherwise remain inaccessible to parts of the research community.

Lessons Learned

- Physical, on-site access to collections remains **essential for high-quality research in the study of religions**, as many key sources are not digitised or require material examination.
- **Place-based research enhances scholarly interpretation**, allowing engagement with manuscripts, archival materials, and artefacts in their historical and cultural context.
- The combination of **physical access and expert mediation** (librarians, archivists, curators, and scholars) significantly improves the efficiency and depth of research.
- Carefully designed digital solutions, when **anchored in physical access**, can expand inclusivity without compromising scholarly standards.
- The Zograf Room at Sofia University demonstrates how RESILIENCE can **bridge access restrictions** by enabling all scholars, including women, to consult otherwise restricted collections on site.
- Transnational Access proves to be **not merely supportive but enabling**, making research possible that would otherwise remain inaccessible through remote or fully digital means.

4.6.5 Summary of Key Success Factors and Challenges

The four case studies highlight complementary dimensions of resilience within the RESILIENCE TNA programme, which also show challenges that are **characteristic of research on religions** and on the **human-centred nature of the research infrastructure**.

- **Religion-specific access challenges:**
 - Case Study 1 illustrates how research on religious communities, archives, and practices often involves heightened sensitivity, restricted materials, and informal access rules that require trust, negotiation, and careful mediation.
 - Effective coordination and expectation management are therefore especially critical in this field.

- **Dealing with crisis and uncertainty**

- Case Study 2 shows how research on religions can be embedded in lived communities and politically sensitive settings, making it particularly vulnerable to external crises and mobility disruptions.
- Continuity was maintained not through physical access alone, but through sustained academic relationships and alternative forms of scholarly exchange.

- **People as a core component of the research infrastructure**

- Case Study 3 demonstrates that complex religious and historical research often depends on personal encounters, local knowledge, and trust-based connections to locate dispersed or poorly documented sources.
- Access enabled by the TNA programme extended beyond facilities to build a network including **people, expertise, and relationships**, and continued even after formal call periods had ended.

- **Inclusive and place-based access to material sources**

- Case Study 4 shows that physical, on-site access to manuscripts and archival collections remains essential in research on religions, particularly where materials are un-digitised, or subject to historical access restrictions, as exemplified by the Zograf Room at Sofia University.
- It also demonstrates how RESILIENCE **enables inclusive access through human mediation and on-site digital consultation**, allowing all scholars, including those otherwise excluded from direct access, to work with unique religious collections within a controlled institutional setting.

Taken together, the case studies show that the strength of the TNA programme lies not only in providing structured access to institutions, but also in fostering **transnational research networks** by connecting researchers with host institutions, local expertise, and wider scholarly communities. **Through human connections, contextual expertise, and sustained engagement, TNA contributes to long-term collaboration and networking effects** that are particularly crucial in the field of research on religions.

4.7 Move Towards a TNA Management Platform

During the preparatory phase (PPP), the organisation and delivery of the TNA programme within RESILIENCE required a considerable administrative and coordination effort. Work Unit Research Services is a resource-intensive unit of the project, with a significant share of personnel time dedicated to the start-up, coordination, and manual management of TNA fellowships, the TNA host network, calls, applications, evaluations, communication, and follow-up of research stays. While this level of effort was appropriate and unavoidable in the initial phase of developing the TNA programme as a prototype service, it also became evident that the existing organisational model is not sustainable in the long term, particularly in view of scaling up TNA activities in future phases.

Against this background, the second core objective of Task 2.6, alongside the operational implementation of the TNA programme itself, was to prepare the transition towards a dedicated TNA Management Platform. From the perspective of RESILIENCE, such a platform is conceived as a centralised access point within the RESILIENCE digital ecosystem, serving TNA Fellows, TNA Hosts, and RESILIENCE members alike. Its overarching purpose is to consolidate all information, services, and workflows related to the TNA programme in one place, including host profiles and collections, calls for applications, fellowship management processes, and the communication of funding opportunities and outcomes.

During the next phase 2026–2028, RESILIENCE will focus on further developing and testing the TNA Management Platform toward future implementation. Building on the prototype developed by ITSERR, activities will concentrate on final testing, usability refinements, and the preparation of technical and organisational documentation, as well as on updating and structuring data related to the TNA Hosting Network for potential integration.

4.7.1 Strategic Objectives of a TNA Management Platform

The move towards a platform-based approach was driven by **three strategic considerations**:

First, the platform is intended to significantly reduce manual administrative effort by automating recurring processes wherever possible, allowing consortium partners to focus their expertise on quality assurance,

programme development, and strategic networking instead of routine management tasks. Second, it aims to improve accessibility and transparency for applicants, enabling researchers to identify suitable hosts, expertise, and collections more efficiently, and to navigate eligibility criteria, application procedures, and evaluation processes within a coherent digital environment. Third, the platform is envisaged as a networking and collaboration space for TNA Hosts, offering a sustainable framework for institutional exchange, shared initiatives, and the potential development of joint funding and research activities beyond individual fellowship stays.

4.7.2 Preparatory Work and Conceptual Planning for the TNA Programme

During the PPP, RESILIENCE concentrated on conceptual preparation and requirements definition. This included mapping existing workflows, identifying bottlenecks in manual procedures, defining which elements could be meaningfully automated (e.g. fellowship applications and evaluations), and clarifying which processes would continue to require human decision-making and negotiation, such as the selection and onboarding of new TNA Hosts. These insights were documented and fed into planning activities for the next project phase.

In this way, the WU RS/TNA actively contributed to the **development of a TNA Management Platform** within the associated ITSERR project, which explicitly builds on the strategic and operational foundations laid out in the RESILIENCE TNA Services Management Plan (D2.5). WP2 participated in the creative and methodological process by providing structured feedback on workflows, user roles, evaluation procedures, and reporting needs, and by reviewing and commenting on successive platform prototypes.

From the perspective of the WU, the ITSERR platform represents a concrete and timely response to the challenges identified during the PPP, as it seeks to digitalise the entire TNA lifecycle, from call publication and proposal submission to peer review, visit organisation, and post-visit assessment, within a role-based, transparent, and traceable system.

The implementation of the usable prototype of the TNA Management Platform itself is **planned for release by the ITSERR project in May 2026**,¹³ aligning with the transition to the next phase of the infrastructure. The preparatory work carried out ensures that RESILIENCE enters this next phase with clearly articulated requirements, tested procedures, and a mature understanding of how digital tools can support a scalable, efficient, and sustainable TNA programme.

5 Strategic Evaluation and Adjustment of the TNA Programme

“Please continue this activity, and it would be excellent if you could identify more places like the Jan Amos Comenius Museum that are open to collaboration with academics.”

(TNA Fellow, Evaluation Sheet, August 2025)

This chapter summarises the strategic evaluation of the Transnational Access (TNA) programme carried out during the preparatory phase. It presents key findings, lessons learned, and resulting adjustments to the TNA model, and includes the Results of KPIs for Transnational Access 2022–2026 to provide an overview of programme performance.

5.1 Mid-Term Review and Strategic Context (2023–2024)

After two years of implementation, the TNA programme was subject to a strategic evaluation in 2023–2024 to inform priorities for the remainder of the preparatory phase. The review in 2023–2024 builded directly on the objectives, governance model, and service principles defined in the **Beta-version of D2.5 – TNA Services Management Plan**¹⁴, in particular **Chapter 2 (Objectives and Scope of TNA)** and **Chapter 3 (TNA**

¹³ For further information on the TNA Management Platform developed by ITSERR, see: Sciortino, Gabriella: TNA Management Platform, in: D’Avenia, Fabrizio/Braghi, Gianmarco (eds.): Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE (ITSERR). A Roadmap of a Project Developed within Digital Humanities for the Information Technology transformation in Religious Studies, Palermo University Press, Palermo 2026 [in press].

¹⁴ The beta deliverable has since been replaced by the final version of D2.5, with comparable content.

Service Model and Procedures). The evaluation was also aligned with the orientation set out in the **TNA Strategy 2023–2026**¹⁵, notably **Section 2 (TNA SWOT Analysis)** and **Section 3 (Strategic Objectives)**.

5.2 Key Findings from the SWOT Analysis

Strengths

- **Access to extensive digital and physical resources for the study of religions, combined with a uniquely broad range of expertise** across the RESILIENCE network, which can be mobilised to support diverse research needs.
- **Strong and sustained demand for structured TNA services within the study of religions**, confirming assumptions formulated in Beta-D2.5, Chapter 2.
- High appreciation of the programme’s emphasis on **personal contact, hospitality, networking, and facilitated access**, identified as a core qualitative feature of TNA also highlighted in TNA Strategy 2023–2026, Section 2.3.
- Building on the **established TNA activities of both the ReReS project and the RESILIENCE Design Phase**, the programme benefited from continuity in structures and processes, enabling a **smooth transition and early adoption**.

Weaknesses

- **Limited or absent funding** in the PPP reduces application numbers and host engagement, a risk anticipated in Beta-D2.5, Chapter 4 (Risks and Mitigation).
- The **coordination and monitoring effort exceeded initial projections**, especially for small host institutions, as discussed in Beta-D2.5, Chapter 3.4 (Operational Requirements).
- The programme currently offers **limited tangible incentives for large, well-established institutions** beyond visibility and networking.

¹⁵ See TNA Strategy 2023–2026, Confidential Report, October 2023.

Opportunities

- RESILIENCE's development as a European-wide research infrastructure provides a **stable foundation for TNA growth** (see TNA Strategy 2023–2026, Section 3.1).
- **Enhanced visibility and internationalisation opportunities for smaller institutions**, and entry pathways for **larger institutions** into future RESILIENCE services.
- Feedback from TNA users confirms **strong appreciation for the continuity and relevance of the programme**, while also highlighting the **opportunity to expand the network of host institutions**. In particular, fellows expressed interest in identifying additional host sites comparable to existing partners that demonstrate a strong openness to academic collaboration and researcher support.
- **Networking effects opening access to follow-up collaborations and external funding**, including MSCA Doctoral Networks and Staff Exchanges (see TNA Strategy 2023–2026, Section 4).
- Building on the emerging **collaboration between EHRI-ERIC and RESILIENCE**, the successful practices of the RESILIENCE TNA programme offer **potential for wider uptake across European TNA initiatives**, including future sharing and reuse through the planned TNA Management Platform.

5.3 Risks and Strategic Lessons Learned

The evaluation confirmed several key risks, including insufficient Fellow applications due to funding constraints, coordination overload caused by many small hosts, and challenges in maintaining a coherent quality profile across a highly diverse host landscape (see D2.5, Chapter 4).

Strategic lessons learned include the need for:

- **Controlled and qualitative growth**,
- More **active engagement by TNA Hosts**, and
- **Digital support tools to enable scalability**, which were already anticipated in D2.5, Chapters 3 and 5.

5.4 Strategic Adjustments and Programme Refinement

Based on the evaluation, the following adjustments, foreseen in the strategy but refined through practice, were prioritised:

- **Development of a TNA Management Platform** to centralise fellow and host management such as applications, status, host profiles, and communication (see D2.5, Chapter 5 on Future Service Development).
- **Controlled expansion of the TNA Host Network**, refining the goals formulated in TNA Strategy 2023–2026, Section 3.2, and limiting expansion to institutions engaged via the enlargement process; expansion towards the MENA region was postponed due to geopolitical developments.
- **Activation of the TNA Host Network**, moving from a predominantly one-directional access model to reciprocal exchange dynamics (see TNA Strategy 2023–2026, Section 3.4).
- **Adjustment of call frequency**: while an ongoing call remains the long-term objective (see D2.5, Chapter 3.2), bi-annual calls were identified as a feasible interim solution until at least 2025.
- **Better exploitation of the existing network** through structured communication, host meetings, and feedback loops (see TNA Strategy 2023–2026, Section 4.2).

5.5 Results KPIs for Transnational Access 2022–2026

This section presents an overview of the key performance indicators (KPIs) used to monitor the implementation and outcomes of Transnational Access within RESILIENCE over the period 2022–2026. It distinguishes between **KPIs defined by the Work Unit Research Services/TNA** and those **set within Work Package 4 Communication and Dissemination**.

5.5.1 KPIs set by Work Unit Research Services/TNA

In the framework of the PPP, WU RS/TNA set the following key performance indicators (KPIs) to assess performance and progress, as detailed in the table below.

WU TNA KPI ID	Key Performance Indicator	Description	Target RESILIENCE PPP, at the end of the project (2026)	Results M1-M46
1	TNA Fellowship Applications	Number of TNA Fellow Applications per cycle	10	18.6 average
2	TNA Calls for Fellows	TNA Calls for Fellows for the PPP	4	5
3	Publications related to TNA	Number of Publications related to TNA	8	12
4	TNA Fellow Evaluations	Number of return rate of TNA Fellow evaluations	40 %	89 % ¹⁶
5	TNA Hosts	Total number of TNA Hosts by the end of the PPP	20	23

Table 4: Key Performance Indicators of WU TNA for TNA fellowships and their results M1–M46

KPI Results WU TNA: The KPI results show that WU TNA exceeded all targets set for the PPP. The average number of TNA Fellowship applications per cycle reached 18.6, significantly surpassing the target of 10, indicating strong and sustained demand. A total of five TNA calls were launched compared to the four planned, demonstrating operational flexibility.

Research output also exceeded expectations, with 12 TNA-related publications produced against a target of eight (with a further 14 publications reported to the WU as forthcoming, and 20 presentations and talks were given at conferences and similar events). These figures reflect only the outputs formally reported to the

¹⁶ By 31 March 2026, 49 evaluation questionnaires had been received, corresponding to an 89 % response rate, based on the 55 fellows who actually undertook TNA activities until this date, see Chapter 6.1.

WU; given the time lag between research stays and publication and the limits of systematic tracking, additional outputs may exist that are not yet captured.

In addition, the return rate for TNA Fellow evaluations reached 89 %, well above the minimum target of 40 %, ensuring a robust basis for quality assessment. Finally, the number of TNA Hosts increased to 23 by the end of the PPP, exceeding the target of 20 and strengthening the hosting network.

Overall, the **WU TNA KPI results** indicate that the implementation of TNA activities progressed in line with, and in several areas beyond, the objectives defined for the PPP.

5.5.2 KPIs set by Work Package 4 Communication and Dissemination

In WP4 Communication and Dissemination, the following KPI’s were set at the beginning of the PPP, with the related goal: “Researchers and host institutions are aware of and react to dissemination concerning the RESILIENCE TNA programme”.

WP4 KPI ID	Key Performance Indicator	Description	Target RESILIENCE PPP, at the end of the project (2026)	Results M1-M4,6
19	TNA Hosts	Number of new TNA hosts from outside the consortium	15	15 ¹⁷
20	Posts	Number of posts on social media related to TNA	180	325
21	TNA Fellowship Applications	Number of TNA Fellowship Applications	30	91

Table 5: Key Performance Indicators set by WP4 for TNA results M1–M4,6

¹⁷ See here Chapter 2.2 Growing the TNA Hosting Network: 2024-2026.

KPI Results WP4 Communication and Dissemination: The WP4 KPIs indicate that communication and outreach activities related to TNA were implemented successfully and, in several areas, exceeded the targets defined for the PPP. The objective of engaging 15 new TNA Hosts from outside the consortium was fully achieved by M46, meeting the target as planned. Communication efforts demonstrated particularly strong performance, with 325 TNA-related posts on social media, significantly exceeding the target of 180, reflecting sustained visibility and outreach.

This is further supported by the number of TNA Fellowship applications linked to WP4 activities, which reached 91 against a target of 30, indicating high responsiveness to communication measures and effective dissemination of TNA calls. Overall, the WP4 KPI results confirm that outreach and engagement objectives were achieved in line with the project's communication strategy.

6 Evaluation and Impact

"My research stay with the RESILIENCE TNA programme at KU Leuven has been one of the most enriching to date. I arrived and was immediately welcomed by the host professor, who introduced me to local experts and to his research team. While in Leuven, I had the opportunity to meet several professors working in my field of medieval religious history. These meetings led to invitations to give lectures and to collaborate, including a possible future postdoc application. My stay in Leuven was also productive for my immediate research goals: at the end of my stay, I successfully submitted a book manuscript for publication (now forthcoming with the Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies Press). In short, my stay with the RESILIENCE programme was highly beneficial for my research and for building academic networks internationally."

(TNA Fellow via email, March 2026)

This chapter assesses the outcomes and impact of the TNA programme through a structured analysis of feedback from TNA Fellows and Host institutions. It examines how the TNA Management Plan has addressed identified challenges, formulates targeted recommendations for future improvement, and provides an overview of the Impact of the TNA programme 2022-2026, including publications, conference contributions, awards, and other tangible results achieved by TNA Fellows.

6.1 TNA Fellow Evaluation: Analysis of Feedback and Outcomes

Following the completion of their Transnational Access research stay, TNA Fellows are invited by the WU TNA team to complete a structured evaluation form as part of the programme’s **monitoring and quality-assurance framework**. This chapter presents a systematic analysis of all **16 evaluation questions and their corresponding responses**, combining quantitative and qualitative feedback.

The analysis is based on **49 completed evaluation forms out of 55 conducted TNA research stays**,¹⁸ providing a solid methodological basis for assessing the effectiveness, outcomes, and user experience of the TNA programme.

The 49 anonymous evaluation responses relate to the following host institutions:

TNA Host Institution	Evaluations received by 31 March 2026	TNA research stays completed by 31 March 2026
Bektashi World Center	0	1
École Pratique des Hautes Études	2	3
Fondazione per le scienze religiose	13	14
ITSERR Consortium	2	4
J.A. Comenius Museum	3	3
KU Leuven and KU Leuven, KADOC	14	16
“Saint Epiphanius” Cultural Academy Cyprus	1	1
Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski ¹⁹	7	6
University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Theology	1	1
University of Münster	1	1

¹⁸ By 31 March 2026, 55 TNA research visits had been completed and were eligible for evaluation. One additional research visit was carried out in April 2026; therefore, some chapters of this report refer to a total of 56 TNA research stays.

¹⁹ There is clearly one stray entry here, but it is not a duplicate; perhaps the TNA host was selected incorrectly. To avoid deleting an entry indiscriminately, it was included in the overall results.

TNA Host Institution	Evaluations received by 31 March 2026	TNA research stays completed by 31 March 2026
University of Sarajevo	2	2
Volos Academy for Theological Studies	3	3
SUM	49	55

Table 6: Number of TNA Fellow Evaluations per TNA Host Institution

The initial questions in the RESILIENCE TNA Scholarship Evaluation Form collect under the title “**Basic Information**” information about the **facility visited** and the **start and end dates of the research stay**.

6.1.1 Analysis of Research support by your TNA host (Questions 1–6)

Questions 1 through 6 can be answered with “Yes/No” or “Yes/No/No, I did not need it for my research”:

Questions	Responses		
	Yes	No	No, I did not need it for my research
1. Were you introduced to (an) expert(s) who offered assistance in using the services provided by your TNA Host?	47	2	(N/A)
2. Were you offered one or more of the services listed below? 2. a. An introduction to the organization of the special collections	41	2	6
2. b. A tutorial on the proper approach to the documents and materials of the special collections/archival documents	36	1	12
2. c. An introduction to the range of digital and physical research tools available onsite to the researcher	36	1	12

Questions	Responses		
	Yes	No	No, I did not need it for my research
3. Were you introduced to (an) expert(s) relevant to your specific research project?	45	4 ²⁰	(N/A)
4. Did you have a discussion with (an) expert(s) related to the research, methodology, (re)sources, and/or network of your specific research project?	44	3	2
5. Did you have a second discussion with an expert concerning the evaluation and analysis of the data obtained during the research activities? ²¹	28	14	7
6. Did using RESILIENCE TNA and working together with the experts available in the TNA-institution(s) help you to refine your methodological approach and/or research content in your research project?	34	6	9
SUM: 392 answers	311	33	48
Percentage	80 %	8 %	12 %

Table 7: Analysis of Research support by TNA hosts (Questions 1–6)

Quantitative Analysis Question 1–6

The evaluation results for Questions 1–6 show a **consistently high level of satisfaction** with the research support provided by TNA Host institutions. The majority of Fellows reported having been introduced to relevant experts

²⁰ The **negative responses in three of the TNA fellows** appear to reflect that, although they were introduced to relevant archivists at the host institutions, they did not associate these contacts with the expert introductions referred to in the evaluation question. **Another TNA fellow** conducted independent research and did not liaise further with the host during the fellowship. The answers point to a more fundamental issue that can arise in some cases, namely differing expectations between fellows and host institutions, which is also noted sometimes with other aspects and should be avoided through clear agreements established at an early stage (see Section 6.2.4).

²¹ This option was provided by some host institutions, depending on project requirements and subject to the availability of relevant experts.

and receiving research assistance tailored to their needs, including introductions to special collections, archival materials, and available physical and digital research tools. Only a small number of respondents indicated that such support was not provided; in most cases, Fellows clarified that certain services were **not required for their specific research project**, rather than unavailable.

Expert engagement emerged as a **central component of the TNA experience**. Most Fellows reported substantive discussions with host-institution experts on research questions, methodology, sources, and scholarly networks. While fewer respondents reported a dedicated follow-up discussion focused on data evaluation and analysis, this was largely explained by Fellows indicating that such a step was not necessary for their research.

Across all six questions, **80 % of responses were positive**, confirming the effectiveness of the TNA support framework. Negative responses accounted for **8 %**, while **12 %** of respondents selected “not needed,” reflecting the methodological diversity of research projects and an overall good alignment between services offered and actual research needs.

Qualitative Feedback: Methodological Refinement (Question 6)

The written responses to Question 6.a confirm that collaboration with host-institution experts significantly contributed to the refinement of fellows’ research. **15 responses explicitly highlight methodological improvements** resulting from in-depth discussions with senior scholars, librarians, and specialists, including clearer research questions, improved analytical frameworks, and refined source interpretation.

12 responses emphasise the discovery of new sources and scholarly literature, often in local languages, that had not been accessible before, broadening the research scope and strengthening awareness of the latest research.

10 responses stress the added value of direct access to physical collections combined with expert guidance, which enabled deeper engagement with manuscripts, archival materials, and rare prints.

Academic exchange beyond individual supervision, such as seminars, presentations, and informal discussions, is mentioned in 10 responses and is frequently linked to concrete outcomes, including conference papers, publications, and new research projects.

Overall, the feedback demonstrates that the TNA framework effectively fosters methodological rigor, intellectual exchange, and sustainable research development.

6.1.2 Evaluation of Organisational Framework, Resources, Overall Experience (Questions 7–13)

The evaluation results for Questions 7–13 confirm a **very high level of satisfaction** with the organisational framework, resources, and overall experience of the TNA fellowship programme.

Communication with TNA Hosts (Question 7) was rated very positively by the large majority of respondents. Out of **49 Fellows**, **42 rated communication as “very good”** and **5 as “good”**, resulting in **96 % positive evaluations**; **2 respondents rated it as “poor”**, with no “satisfactory” ratings. Qualitative feedback (30 written comments) highlights proactive and clear communication, early planning support, prompt responses, and the personal engagement of host staff. Fellows particularly valued assistance with scheduling, accommodation, access arrangements, and integration into local research environments. The few critical remarks refer to isolated cases and remain exceptions.²²

Accommodation (Question 8) also received very positive feedback. Among **33 respondents** for whom accommodation was relevant, **22 rated it “very good”** and **11 “good”**, with **no negative ratings**. Where accommodation was not provided, fellows arranged it independently, often with informal support from host institutions.

Availability of research materials (Question 9) was rated positively by over **90 %** of Fellows: **32 “very good”** and **12 “good”** out of **49 responses**, with **3 “satisfactory”** and **2 “poor”** ratings. Qualitative feedback emphasises the breadth, multilingual nature, and quality of collections, as well as access to rare or otherwise inaccessible materials. Reported limitations were mainly linked to highly specialised topics or archival organisation and were often mitigated through expert support.

Planned dissemination of research results (Questions 10–11) provided the WU TNA with an overview of intended publications and expected timelines.²³

²² As the PPP specifically aimed at prototyping the TNA management programme, these two cases, though being exceptions, were substantially used to improve our internal communication and procedures to more easily follow up in the future when such cases reoccur (see also Section 6.2.4).

²³ Information on publications and other outcomes resulting from RESILIENCE TNA can be found in Chapter 6.3 and the list of outcomes is provided in Appendix 2, Chapter 9.2.

The **overall rating of the TNA experience (Question 12)** reflects an exceptionally high level of satisfaction: the **49 Fellows awarded an average score of 9.2 out of 10**, indicating that expectations were met or exceeded.

Finally, **identified strengths of the TNA programme (Question 13)** show highly consistent qualitative patterns.

- **20 responses** highlight the quality, competence, and engagement of host institutions and supervisors, with **at least 5 Fellows** (notably early-career researchers) emphasising the value of being connected to experts without prior contacts.
- **15 responses** identify communication and organisation as key strengths, citing clarity, responsiveness, flexibility, and effective coordination with the RESILIENCE team.
- **12 responses** underline access to libraries, archives, and workspaces.
- **10 responses** stress strong professional support from librarians and archivists.
- **10 responses** emphasise opportunities for academic exchange, networking, and dissemination, often linked to concrete outcomes such as presentations, publications, and follow-up projects.
- Several Fellows explicitly refer to the **welcoming and supportive atmosphere** as an important factor for research productivity.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the organisational, infrastructural, and human dimensions of the TNA programme function very effectively and contribute decisively to a positive and high-quality research experience.

6.1.3 Analysis of Suggestions for Improvement (Question 14)

Out of 49 respondents, a **clear majority (27 Fellows)** explicitly stated that they **could not identify any aspect that should be improved**, using formulations such as “nothing”, “everything was perfect”, or equivalent. This confirms the very high satisfaction level reported throughout the evaluation.

22 respondents provided suggestions for improvements. All critical remarks are related to **financial scope and structural limitations**, and framed as suggestions to further enhance the research possibilities. **No criticism concerned scientific quality, host institutions, or organisational performance.**

6.1.3.1 Overview of Key Issues and Mitigation Measures Identified in the TNA Fellow Evaluation

The following table presents a **consolidated overview of the identified critical points**, together with the corrective actions already implemented or planned.

Critical Points Identified	Corrective Actions & Mitigating Measures taken in the PPP
<p>Funding and financial coverage were the most frequently mentioned areas for improvement, raised by 13 respondents. These Fellows suggested higher funding levels, longer funded stays, broader coverage of accommodation and living costs, or increased flexibility in the use of funds.</p>	<p>To address funding-related constraints, the WU TNA encouraged in-kind contributions from the host institutions. Sofia University and KUL provided limited funded research stays, other hosts supported Fellows through free (Fscire) or reduced-cost accommodation, access to facilities, free copy services, coffee etc, or additional logistical support.</p> <p>Based on this experience, the provision of funded TNA activities is an important objective of the RESILIENCE Implementation Phase, with the aim of strengthening financial support for future Fellows, and foreseen in the TNA management plan (Deliverable D2.5).</p>
<p>Accommodation-related support was mentioned by 8 respondents, either as a request for guaranteed lodging or for stronger financial contributions in high-cost locations.</p>	<p>See above.</p>

Critical Points Identified	Corrective Actions & Mitigating Measures taken in the PPP
<p>Clearer advance information on grant conditions (what is included or excluded) was noted by 6 respondents, particularly regarding accommodation, reimbursement rules, and funding limits.</p>	<p>To address the need for clearer advance information, the WU TNA has revised the text of the call for applications on its website and in its press releases, providing even clearer guidance on which costs are included or excluded.</p> <p>The information provided in the call for applications and in communications prior to the visit has been aligned to ensure greater transparency and enable fellows to plan effectively.</p>
<p>Longer or more flexible research stays were suggested by 4 respondents, especially for archival and manuscript-based research requiring exploratory phases.</p>	<p>The TNA programme already applies a flexible approach to the duration of research stays, allowing Hosts to adapt access periods based on research needs. Across 54 TNA Fellows, a total of 785 access days were granted, with stays ranging from 5 to 39 days (average 14.5 days). While the text of the TNA Call suggests “typically two weeks” as a guideline, longer stays were approved in justified cases.</p>
<p>Post-visit follow-up and networking opportunities were mentioned by 2 respondents as a potential added value.</p>	<p>To strengthen post-visit follow-up and networking, the creation of a TNA alumni network is already planned. Former Fellows were invited to subscribe in order to remain connected, facilitate ongoing exchange, and promote future collaboration within the RESILIENCE community.</p>

Table 8: Critical Points from TNA fellow Evaluations with Corrective Actions and Mitigating Measures

6.1.4 Consent to Feedback Sharing and Additional Remarks (Questions 15–16)

Responses to **Question 15** show an **almost unanimous willingness to “Share evaluation feedback”** with the TNA Host institutions. Out of **49 respondents, 48 consented** to the sharing of their feedback, with **only one respondent declining**. This result indicates a high level of trust in the evaluation process and its role in quality assurance and programme improvement.

Regarding **Question 16, 20 out of 49 Fellows** provided **“Additional remarks”**. These comments were exclusively positive or constructive and can be clearly categorised as follows:

- **11 respondents** submitted purely positive feedback, expressing gratitude for the TNA Fellowship and highlighting the quality of the research experience, the scientific and personal support received, and the overall value of the programme. Several Fellows emphasised the lasting impact of the fellowship on their academic work and expressed interest in participating again.
- **4 respondents** explicitly stated that they had no further remarks, often accompanied by brief words of thanks, indicating satisfaction without additional comments.
- **5 respondents** combined positive feedback with forward-looking suggestions. These focused on interest in continuing collaboration, the importance of sustained access to rare materials, one minor technical issue related to the evaluation form, opportunities for research dissemination, and interest in stronger support for publication or career development.

No negative or critical remarks were submitted in this section. Overall, the responses confirm strong satisfaction, trust in programme governance, and a constructive engagement of Fellows with the evaluation process.

6.1.5 Conclusion and Overall Evaluation Summary (Questions 1–16)

The evaluation is based on **49 responses out of 54 completed TNA research stays** (until 31 March 2026), representing a **high response rate** and providing a solid and representative basis for the findings.

The analyses of **Questions 1–16** show a consistently positive assessment of the Transnational Access Fellowship programme. Fellows reported strong engagement with host experts and high satisfaction with the support received during their research stays (Questions 1–6). Communication with Host institutions and the organisation of visits were evaluated very positively (Questions 7 and 12), while access to research materials and infrastructures was rated good to very good in the large majority of cases (Questions 8 and 9).

The programme's impact on methodological development, research outcomes, and networking is clearly reflected in both the quantitative results and the qualitative feedback provided throughout the survey (Questions 6, 11, 13, and 16). The overall assessment is confirmed by the high average satisfaction score of **9.2 out of 10** (Question 12).

Critical points raised by Fellows were limited in number and mainly concerned funding scope and financial coverage, the duration and flexibility of research stays, and the clarity of advance information on grant conditions (Questions 14 and 16). These issues were addressed through flexible implementation practices, in-kind contributions by Host institutions, and targeted corrective measures. Additional remarks further underline the high level of satisfaction and the perceived added value of the programme (Question 16).

Overall, the evaluation shows that the TNA programme **directly supported the refinement of research methodologies, enabled access to unique collections and expertise, fostered scholarly networking, and contributed to concrete research outputs such as presentations, publications, and new project plans**, thereby delivering measurable benefits for participating researchers within the RESILIENCE research infrastructure.

It is particularly noteworthy that TNA Fellows reported this high level of satisfaction, despite the fact that only a limited number of research stays were fully funded. This finding underlines the **strong relevance and added value of Transnational Access for research on religions**, where access to specialised collections, expert knowledge, and unique research infrastructures often outweighs financial constraints and remains essential for advancing scholarship in the field.

6.2 TNA Host Evaluation: Analysis of Feedback and Outcomes

This section presents the results of the TNA Host Evaluation, capturing the perspectives of host institutions on the organisation, implementation, and outcomes of TNA research stays. Complementing the Fellow Evaluation, it focuses on **hosting conditions, communication, cooperation, and institutional workload, and provides evidence-based insights into the strengths, challenges, and improvement needs** of the TNA framework **from the hosts' point of view**.

6.2.1 Scope, Participation, and Hosting Conditions (Questions 1–4)

To support quality assurance and continuous programme improvement, host institutions were invited to complete a TNA Host Evaluation Form in **September 2024** and again in **September 2025**. In total, **23 host evaluations** were received (**8 in 2024, 15 in 2025**). Of these, **14 respondents had hosted TNA Fellows**, while hosts without fellows were also invited to participate, as the survey included questions on communication with the RESILIENCE TNA team.

All **23 respondents** reported **no changes** to their designated TNA coordinator or contact person. Hosts confirmed that all core TNA services, as workspace, access to collections, meetings with experts, and organisational support, were provided **without difficulties**, and no challenges were reported in delivering these baseline services.

Among the **14 hosts who received fellows**, additional services included: **11** monitoring meetings with TNA coordinators or contact persons, **9** collection introductions or tutorials, **5** training sessions on specific tools or services, **9** academic events during the stay, and **1** case of accommodation provision.

6.2.2 Communication, Daily Cooperation, and Expert Access (Questions 5–7)

Communication during visit preparation (Question 5) received a mixed but overall positive assessment, with an average score of **3** (scale: 1 is excellent, 5 is poor). Out of **18 written comments**, **10 hosts** described communication as “excellent”, “smooth”, or “timely”. Recurring challenges related to **scheduling changes (5 responses)**, **delayed replies (2 responses)**, and **misunderstandings about funding conditions (2 responses)**.

Daily cooperation during the stay (Question 6) was rated by all **14 hosts who received fellows**, with an average score of **3.2** and **five ratings of “poor” (5)**. At the same time, **9 written responses** described collegial, problem-free cooperation, including **five** explicitly stating that there were “no problems at all”. Difficulties reported (**6 responses**) mainly concerned earlier clarification of research needs (**3 cases**), staff availability expectations (**2 cases**), and one request for post-visit digitisation not foreseen in the TNA framework.

Arranging meetings with experts (Question 7) was generally easy to very easy, reflected in a high average score of **4.4 (1 × 2, 5 × 4, 8 × 5)**. In **13 written responses**, **10 hosts** reported no difficulties; isolated challenges related to expert availability or topic complexity.

6.2.3 Workload, Capacity, and Overall Assessment (Questions 8–15)

Reported challenges in arranging TNA stays (**Question 8**) were mainly organisational: poor communication with fellows (**3 hosts**), high time investment (**2 hosts**), and financial or accommodation-related issues (noted in **8 “Other” responses**). No difficulties were reported with RESILIENCE TNA team communication.

Estimated workload per visit (**Question 9**) was as follows:

- **12 hosts**: 1–10 hours
- **7 hosts**: 10–20 hours
- **2 hosts**: 20–30 hours
- **2 hosts**: 30–40 hours

This corresponds to an average of approximately **12.7 hours per visit**. Expected annual hosting capacity (**Question 10**) ranged from **1 to 10 fellows**, with an **average of 3.3 fellows per host**.

The **overall hosting experience (Question 11)** was rated positively: excluding 9 respondents without a stay, the **average rating was 4.21 (out of 5)**, with 6 hosts awarding the highest score (5), 5 rating 4, and 3 rating 3; no ratings of 1 or 2 were given. **Hosts highlighted intellectual exchange, institutional visibility, and future cooperation**, while **challenges** related mainly to **stay duration and accommodation costs**.

Support from the **RESILIENCE TNA team (Question 12)** received very high ratings: **13 ratings of 5, 5 ratings of 4**, and only **three lower ratings** (one each of 3, 2, and 1). Written feedback praised fast response times, clear guidance, and continuous availability.

Key strengths identified by hosts (**Question 13**) include communication quality and personal support (**10 responses**), clear documentation and workflows (**4 responses**), and well-organised calls and coordination (**4 responses**).

Areas for improvement (**Question 14**) focused mainly on funding clarity and fellow allowances (**6 responses**) and clearer procedures for new hosts (**4 responses**), while **11 respondents** reported no improvement needs or could not assess.

Additional remarks (**Question 15**) reinforced overall satisfaction, with hosts highlighting trust in the programme, interest in further support measures, and suggestions for joint dissemination strategies.

6.2.4 Overview of Key Issues and Mitigation Measures Identified in the TNA Host Evaluation

The following table provides an **overview of the key issues** identified in the TNA host evaluations and the **corresponding mitigation measures**:

Critical Points Identified	Corrective Actions & Mitigating Measures taken in the PPP
<p>Repeated changes to visit dates and unclear scheduling result in a significant time commitment for the hosts</p>	<p>Introduce strong guidance on acceptable date changes and clearer timelines agreed before confirmation of the stay.</p> <p>⇒ Clear rules regarding postponements and date changes are already specified in the “Terms and Conditions” document; however, hosts often accept exceptions in order to allow fellows to carry out their visit.</p>
<p>Unclear expectations regarding services included in TNA</p>	<p>Provide a concise, mandatory checklist outlining services covered during and after the stay, shared with both hosts and fellows.</p> <p>⇒ “TNA Fellow Rights” and “TNA Fellow Obligations” are explicitly stated in the “TNA Fellow Grant Agreement.</p> <p>⇒ With the TNA management platform, we aim to more structurally follow up on the clarification, documentation, and mutual understanding of expectations between fellows and host institutions throughout the TNA lifecycle.</p>

Critical Points Identified	Corrective Actions & Mitigating Measures taken in the PPP
<p>Insufficient advance communication of research needs</p>	<p>Require fellows to submit a structured research needs statement prior to arrival and encourage early host-fellow consultation.</p> <p>⇒ Addressed through direct communication between host and fellow, not centrally managed by RESILIENCE; the workflow specifies that research needs should be agreed at an early stage.</p>
<p>Misunderstandings about funding and allowances</p>	<p>Make funding conditions explicit and visible in calls, application materials, and host-fellow communication; consider standardised wording or highlighted notices.</p> <p>⇒ The absence of mobility funding (for most host, with exception) was clearly stated in the TNA Calls for 2022–2025 on the website (main call page, individual host pages under “Benefits”, and press releases); nonetheless, this information is sometimes overlooked in practice, leading to misunderstandings or additional funding requests.</p>
<p>Variability in daily cooperation styles between TNA host and TNA fellow</p>	<p>Define minimum expectations for interaction and support during the stay while allowing flexibility for independent research approaches.</p> <p>⇒ “TNA Fellow Rights” and “TNA Fellow Obligations” are clearly stated in the “TNA Fellow Grant Agreement.”</p>
<p>Initial uncertainty among first-time hosts</p>	<p>Provide simple onboarding materials and step-by-step guidance, complemented by optional information workshops for hosts.</p> <p>⇒ Information workshops are conducted on a yearly basis, as well as bimonthly meetings of the WU TNA, and the TNA team offers continuous support.</p>

Critical Points Identified	Corrective Actions & Mitigating Measures taken in the PPP
Need for systematic peer exchange among hosts	<p>Periodic experience-sharing formats (online or in-person) to support mutual learning and alignment of practices.</p> <p>⇒ Workshops and bimonthly WU TNA meetings provide regular opportunities for peer exchange and alignment of practices.</p> <p>⇒ However, the need for other formats should be assessed regularly.</p>

Table 9: TNA Host Evaluation: Critical Points, Corrective Actions, Mitigating Measures

6.2.5 Conclusion and Evaluation Summary (Questions 1–15)

The TNA Host Evaluation confirms a **high overall level of engagement and satisfaction** among host institutions participating in the RESILIENCE Transnational Access programme. Hosts consistently highlighted the quality of communication, the reliability of support provided by the RESILIENCE TNA team, and the intellectual value of hosting external researchers. The evaluation demonstrates that, for most institutions, TNA hosting is perceived as a **manageable and rewarding activity**, well integrated into existing academic and infrastructural work.

At the same time, the feedback identifies **recurrent structural challenges**, particularly related to funding clarity, scheduling stability, and the need for earlier definition of research needs and expectations. These issues are largely external to the core hosting experience and point to areas where improved communication and clearer framing of conditions can further strengthen programme implementation.

The evaluation of the TNA Hosts must be situated within the specific structural framework of the RESILIENCE TNA programme. **TNA Hosts are autonomous institutions** with their own long-standing working histories, internal procedures, and institutional priorities. As such, their participation in the TNA programme necessarily entails a balancing act between adhering to the terms and conditions defined by RESILIENCE and maintaining established institutional practices. This balancing act is further shaped by the fact that **TNA Hosts do not receive**

financial support for hosting fellows, which places greater emphasis on **mutual commitment, clearly articulated expectations, and the perceived return of participation for all parties involved**. Ensuring alignment under these conditions therefore requires continuous dialogue, transparency, and realistic framing of roles and responsibilities.

Overall, the host perspectives complement the positive assessments provided by TNA Fellows and underline the importance of **clear workflows, personal support, and realistic expectation management**. The findings provide a robust evidence base for ongoing refinements of the TNA framework and inform the corrective actions and mitigation measures presented in the corresponding overview table.

6.3 TNA Fellow Outputs: Publications, Presentations, Awards, and Media Coverage

During the RESILIENCE PPP, TNA Fellows produced a substantial body of scholarly and public outputs, including **13 publications** (9 open-access publications and 4 not in open access), with **13 further publications announced as forthcoming**, alongside **20 conference papers, presentations, and similar outputs**. In addition, **36 news items** featuring TNA-related activities were published on the RESILIENCE website and in external media. The figures reflect outputs **reported by TNA fellows up to 31 March 2026**; a comprehensive list is provided in **Appendix 2**.

7 Communication and Dissemination

“Although there is a time and space barrier, teamwork is at a very high level, which gives good results. Also, timely communication and communication skills of the members of the RESILIENCE project is something extremely important that was taken care of.”

(TNA Host in the Evaluation Sheet, August 2024)

Communication and dissemination play a central role in ensuring the visibility, accessibility, and uptake of the RESILIENCE Transnational Access (TNA) Programme. This chapter presents the Communication Strategy Frame (6.1) and Workflow (6.2), the main activities carried out using communication channels and dissemination measures (6.3), and the resulting reach of TNA-related dissemination efforts (6.4).

7.1 Communication Strategy Frame for the RESILIENCE TNA Programme

Communication activities for the RESILIENCE TNA Programme are guided by a dedicated Communication Strategy Frame developed by WP₄ Communication and Dissemination in close cooperation with WU RS/TNA. The frame provides a structured yet flexible basis for planning and implementing TNA-related communication and outreach activities.

The TNA Communication Strategy Frame forms part of RESILIENCE’s overall communication approach, which is organised into three complementary frames: a general Communication Strategy Frame, a frame addressing Eastern Europe and the Balkans, and a specific frame for TNA. Each frame is structured around **eight key elements** describing **the internal and external context, stakeholders, resources, as well as the project’s vision, ambition, accountability, and gameplan**, ensuring coherence across communication activities.

The Communication Strategy Frame has been regularly updated in specific consortium meetings to reflect the evolving stage of the TNA service. The latest version (03.00), finalised in December 2023 and included in Deliverable D_{4.2} “Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan”,²⁴ provides the reference framework for TNA communication and dissemination activities during the PPP.²⁵

²⁴ See [RESILIENCE WP₄ D_{4.2} CDEP 01.00 FINAL](#), Chapters 2.1 and 3.3, and the figure on p. 31.

²⁵ Since for RESILIENCE TIP Phase (2026-2028) no TNA scholarships will be offered, frame for the TNA programme has been replaced by a framework that generally addresses services rather than TNA specifically (Deliverable D_{4.3}, January 2026).

Figure 4: Communication Strategy Frame RESILIENCE TNA Programme, version 03.00

7.2 Communication Workflow for the RESILIENCE TNA Programme

The communication activities for the RESILIENCE TNA Programme are further operationalised through a dedicated TNA Communication Workflow,²⁶ last updated in December 2025.

Building on earlier experience and feedback from former TNA fellows of the previous RelReS project, the **RESILIENCE TNA Communication Workflow** was developed within WP4 Communication and Dissemination in cooperation with WU RS/TNA. The workflow translates the overarching communication

²⁶ RESILIENCE_WP4_TNA_Communication_Workflow_FINAL_02.00, 30.12.2025 (Confidential).

strategy into a **set of clearly defined, repeatable actions, clarifying responsibilities and timing across partners.**

The workflow is structured along the different phases of the TNA lifecycle and covers **communication activities before, during, and after each Call for Applications**, as well as **before, during, and following individual TNA research stays.**

For each phase, it defines key tasks related to content preparation, dissemination across RESILIENCE channels, coordination between WP4 and TNA coordinators, and interaction with applicants, fellows, and host institutions. **Particular emphasis is placed on consistent visibility of TNA opportunities, regular communication during research stays, and follow-up dissemination of outputs and impact.**

In addition, the workflow integrates the **systematic collection and use of feedback** through evaluation forms for TNA fellows and hosts, ensuring that communication activities are informed by experience and support continuous improvement. Thus the TNA Programme Communication Workflow provides a **practical framework that supports coordinated, transparent, and effective communication and dissemination** throughout the full duration of the TNA cycle.

7.3 Communication Channels and Dissemination Measures

WP4 Communication and Dissemination continuously supported Work Unit Research Services/TNA by developing communication content and materials and by coordinating the dissemination of calls and news related to the Transnational Access Programme.

7.3.1 Online Presence of TNA on the RESILIENCE Website

The RESILIENCE website serves as the central information hub for the TNA Programme. A dedicated section provides comprehensive information on TNA calls, eligibility criteria, application procedures, and timelines. From the **main page for the TNA Call**, [Call for Applications for RESILIENCE TNA Fellowships 2025-2026 - RESILIENCE](#), users are directed to **individual subpages for each active TNA Host**, for example the RESILIENCE coordinator FSCIRE Bologna: [Call for Applications for RESILIENCE TNA Fellowships 2025-2026 - RESILIENCE](#).

Each host page follows a clear and consistent structure, presenting essential information for prospective TNA fellows, including: “Benefits for TNA Users”, “About Us”, “Our Collections”, “Libraries”, “Research Groups and Expertise”, “Explore National Libraries and Museums”, “Your TNA Contact”, as well as other relevant information and, where available, multimedia content.

Figure 5: Still from a Video on the RESILIENCE TNA Host page: [TNA@Fscire: Why Coming to Bologna?](#)

Figure 6: Still from a Video on the RESILIENCE TNA Host page: [TNA@University of Sarajevo: About Us](#)

These TNA Host pages are developed in close cooperation with TNA Host Contact Persons and Coordinators and are regularly updated. Considerable effort is invested in ensuring that the information is easily accessible, especially as host websites and catalogues are often available only in local languages or are not easily navigable.

The website also hosts the **TNA Application portal** (currently closed) as well as the **Evaluation Surveys for TNA fellows and TNA hosts**.

After the last TNA Call for Applications, the RESILIENCE website was updated (February 2026). The TNA Programme is now shown on the [service page](#) (following Deliverable D2.2)²⁷, and indicated as one of the four (future) core services of RESILIENCE.

²⁷ See D2.2 User Services Catalogue 02.00: [RESILIENCE WP2 D2.2 UserServicesCatalogue 02.00 FINAL.pdf](#)

Services

Ahead of the launch of the RESILIENCE portal - which will offer a wide range of services - you can already explore the services our partners provide to support research in the [study of religion](#). This overview is based on Deliverable D2.2, the User Services Catalogue, which is available in our Zenodo Community.

Community Services

<p>Community Service</p> <p>Bibliographies & Aggregators</p> <p>8 Items</p>	<p>Community Service</p> <p>Digital Collections & Databases</p> <p>25 Items</p>	<p>Community Service</p> <p>Digitization & Material Analysis</p> <p>3 Items</p>
<p>Community Service</p> <p>Education & Training</p> <p>7 Items</p>	<p>Community Service</p> <p>Physical Libraries & Archives</p> <p>48 Items</p>	<p>Community Service</p> <p>Research Tools & Applications</p> <p>11 Items</p>

Core Services

<p>Core Service</p> <p>Online Discovery Environment RelReSearch</p>	<p>Core Service</p> <p>RESILIENCE Community on Zenodo</p>	<p>Core Service</p> <p>Training Programme</p>	<p>Core Service</p> <p>Transnational Access Programme</p>
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Figure 7: Current status of the [RESILIENCE service page](#), featuring Community Services (provided in-kind) and Core Services

7.3.2 Dissemination of the TNA Calls

Dissemination activities related to TNA calls were coordinated and implemented by WP4 through press releases and newsletters. Consortium partners were invited to translate and disseminate these press releases in their national languages, thereby extending the geographical reach and visibility of TNA opportunities.

7.3.3 Development of Communication Materials

Dedicated communication materials, including flyers, were developed by WP4 together with WU RS/TNA to promote both TNA fellow calls as well as calls for hosting institutions. These materials complemented online dissemination activities and supported targeted outreach efforts.

Figure 8: Flyer to promote a TNA Fellow Call

Figure 9: Social media format to promote a TNA Call

7.3.4 Communication on TNA Fellowships and Research Stays

In cooperation with WP4, communication on individual TNA fellowships was carried out through news items and blog posts on the RESILIENCE website. Until March 2026, 24 items highlighting TNA fellows, their research stays, experiences, and results were published in the RESILIENCE [News](#) and [Blog](#) sections. For an overview, see Appendix 2, Section 9.2.4.

In addition, at least 325 social media posts related to the RESILIENCE TNA Programme were published across Facebook, Instagram, X, LinkedIn, and YouTube, contributing to sustained visibility and engagement.

7.3.5 General News Items and Multimedia Content

Further communication activities included general news items introducing the RESILIENCE TNA Programme, video content, and thematic posts focusing on specific TNA hosts, funding opportunities, and fellows' experiences. These activities supported broader awareness of TNA services within and beyond the academic community:

- RESILIENCE/TNA Hosts: Introduction of the RESILIENCE TNA Programme: [RESILIENCE TNA Video 01 00 June 2022 - YouTube](#) (18 June 2022)
- About ITSERR TNA Hosts: [Attractive Conditions TNA Fellowship at ITSERR Consortium Partners - RESILIENCE](#) (19 October 2024); [Attractive Conditions TNA Fellowship at ITSERR Consortium Partners - RESILIENCE](#) (17 March 2025)
- About TNA Host Sofia and Funding: [€ 1000 Funding for a TNA Fellowship in Sofia - RESILIENCE](#) (21 March 2025)
- [How do Scholars Experience their TNA Stay? - RESILIENCE](#) (05 April 2025)

References to TNA-related news items and publications are provided in the Appendix 2 "Outputs and Outcomes of the TNA Fellowships RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase", Chapter 9.2.4: Communication and Dissemination Outputs, while information specific to the media coverage of TNA calls for fellows and hosts is addressed in this deliverable in Chapter 3.2.

7.4 Total Reach of Communication and Dissemination Activities for Transnational Access

A total of 128,857 people were reached through communication activities specifically related to TNA during M1–M41 (June 2022 to October 2025),²⁸ out of an overall reach of 670,744 people achieved by RESILIENCE communication and dissemination activities during this period.²⁹ All consortium partners were invited to disseminate TNA-related press releases, while TNA host institutions outside the consortium also contributed to dissemination, although their reach is not included in the RESILIENCE reporting figures.

²⁸ In M41 (October 2025), the most recent data collection was carried out by WP4; the final figures for the current project phase will be available after May 2026.

²⁹ See RESILIENCE Report WP4 Statistics M1-M41, Confidential Appendix to D4.3: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan RESILIENCE PPP, looking forward: [RESILIENCE WP4 CDEP D4.3 01.00 FINAL.pdf](#).

The figure below illustrates the **media channels** through which audiences were reached within the TNA communication framework. **Press releases**, which primarily promoted the five calls for applications, accounted for the largest share of the reach (**99,162 people**), followed by **social media (14,172)**, the **RESILIENCE website (7,395)**, and other **communication activities (7,322)**. Events and attendance contributed a more limited reach (**30**). The high impact of press releases is partly due to their publication on major dissemination platforms, notably [H-Soz-Kult](#) and IDW online ([Informationsdienst Wissenschaft - Nachrichten](#)), where all five TNA calls for applications were promoted. **Flyers and other printed promotional materials are not included** in these figures in order to avoid double counting, as their audiences are typically also reached through other communication channels already accounted for.

Figure 10: Type of Media by which people are reached in the communication framework of TNA in M1–M41

8 Conclusion

"We travel to learn; and I have never been in any country where they did not do something better than we do it, think some thoughts better than we think, catch some inspiration from heights above our own."

(Pioneering Astronomer Maria Mitchell in her diary 1871)

This deliverable presents a comprehensive analysis of the pilot Transnational Access activities implemented during the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase. In line with the Grant Agreement, it evaluates the results of the TNA programme, identifies difficulties and risks encountered during implementation, and assesses opportunities for future development. The findings confirm that TNA has evolved from a conceptual service into a **tested and operationally mature component** of the RESILIENCE research infrastructure, enhancing access to resources relevant to the study of religions and fostering scholarly networking.

A central reference point throughout this process has been the **TNA Services Management Plan (D2.5)**. The challenges encountered during the Preparatory Phase did not remain abstract observations but were continuously addressed through the management logic, governance structures, and adaptive workflows defined in that plan.

Feedback from TNA Fellows, TNA Hosts, and internal monitoring consistently informed refinements to call design, host admission procedures, communication processes, and evaluation mechanisms. In this way, implementation and management planning developed iteratively and in close alignment.

One of the key challenges was that the **TNA stays were not financially funded beside exceptions** provided in-kind by some of the TNA hosts. As a result, participation depended largely on researchers' ability to secure external funding or institutional support, which may have limited access for early-career researchers and applicants with fewer financial resources. This may have influenced the duration and scope of some TNA stays. Dedicated funding for TNA stays would therefore be important for future programme phases, in order to ensure broader accessibility and maximise research impact.

Another challenge identified early on concerned the **limited flexibility created by a single annual TNA call**. While an ongoing call model was recognised as the ideal solution for enabling rapid and responsive access, the resource intensity of manual coordination made this unfeasible at the Preparatory Phase stage. In response, the programme shifted to **two calls per year**, which significantly increased flexibility for applicants and helped establish continuity and momentum. This adjustment proved effective not only in

widening access opportunities for TNA fellows but also in strengthening and stabilising the emerging **TNA Host and Fellow network**, thereby supporting the longer-term sustainability of the programme.

A second core challenge related to the **admission and onboarding of new TNA Host institutions**. As the hosting network expanded, it became essential to maintain high-quality standards while accommodating institutional diversity. The admission workflow was therefore continuously refined, resulting in a procedure that is efficient, transparent, and strongly communication-oriented.

The **administrative and coordination effort** required to operate TNA during the Preparatory Phase was substantial. While this was appropriate for a prototyping stage, evaluations clearly showed that the manual model is not sustainable at scale. The strategic response to this challenge was the preparation of a **TNA Management Platform**, which is currently developed in the ITSERR project in close alignment with the RESILIENCE Work Unit TNA. The platform, currently in the prototyping phase, is designed to centralise calls, applications, evaluations, host data, visit management, and reporting. Its implementation will significantly reduce personnel effort, improve transparency and traceability, support impact assessment, and enhance accessibility for both fellows and hosts. This directly operationalises several objectives formulated in [D2.5 RESILIENCE TNA Services Management Plan](#).

Evaluation results from both TNA Fellows and TNA Hosts strongly confirm the effectiveness of the TNA Management Programme. Fellows highlighted the **importance of facilitated access to physical collections, expert guidance, and human networks**, while TNA Hosts emphasised the **quality of coordination, documentation, and support provided by the TNA team**. Where challenges emerged, particularly in scheduling stability, expectation management, and funding clarity, these were consistently addressed through procedural adjustments and informed the corrective and mitigating measures documented in this deliverable. The convergence between evaluation findings and management responses demonstrates a **high degree of internal coherence** between planning and execution.

During the Preparatory Phase, RESILIENCE was also able to **go beyond the initial scope** of the TNA programme. The testing of **staff exchanges**, the inclusion of **GLAM institutions as TNA Hosts**, and the implementation of **fully funded calls in cooperation with ITSERR** provided valuable insights into alternative access formats and funding models. These initiatives broadened the conceptual understanding of TNA and will directly inform future service design.

Looking ahead, the results presented in this report provide a solid foundation for the next phase of RESILIENCE. **Key priorities** include the **final testing and rollout of the TNA Management Platform**, the

consolidation and expansion of the **TNA Hosting Network**, and the systematic integration of host data, resources, and expertise into a unified digital environment.

Further steps include the creation of a **TNA alumni network**, deeper embedding of hosts within national nodes, interim agreements with TNA Hosts, and expanded collaboration with other European research infrastructures in the humanities and heritage, including EHRI, E-RIHS, and the SSHOC cluster. In parallel, preparatory work will begin on a **Physical Access Platform**, integrating all on-site services and incorporating the TNA Management Platform as a core component.

In conclusion, the TNA programme implemented during the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase has proven its **scientific relevance, operational feasibility, and strategic value** for research on religions. Through systematic evaluation, responsive management, and extensive prototyping, RESILIENCE has established a robust and sustainable framework for Transnational Access that is ready to support a fully operational research infrastructure in the next phase.

9 Appendix

The appendix provides supplementary material to this report:

Section 9.1 presents the **TNA Host Memorandum of Understanding for the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase**,³⁰ while **Section 9.2** outlines the **Outputs and Outcomes of the TNA Fellowships** implemented during this phase.

³⁰ Reference to the **Memorandum of Understanding for the next phase** is provided in Appendix 7.1 of Deliverable D2.5 TNA Services Management Plan.

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9.1 Appendix 1:
TNA Host Memorandum of Understanding
RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase

Preamble

This Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) is entered into by and between:

(A) European Research Infrastructure on Religious Studies (hereafter RESILIENCE).

(B) TNA HOST

The RESILIENCE Transnational Access Programme (TNA) offers physical and virtual access to an expanding network of European institutions and libraries. Its aim is to facilitate and foster easy access to sources, resources, expertise and services for researchers in the study of religions in all their synchronic and diachronic variety, as well as promoting and disseminating collections, institutions, and archives. Considering the desire of the TNA HOST to become a RESILIENCE TNA host, this Memorandum of Understanding lists the mutual roles and responsibilities of each party in taking part to the TNA Programme and is intended to promote and ensure the excellence of the RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship Programme.

Roles and Responsibilities

Commitments of TNA HOST

To ensure excellence RESILIENCE asks hosts to provide a minimum of duties, which can be summarised as follows:

1. Appoint a RESILIENCE TNA coordinator and a TNA Contact Person. These roles may be performed by one person, if preferred:

TNA Coordinator	TNA Contact Person
Reviews Applications	Point of Contact for TNA Scholar
Provides a letter of invitation	Responsible for practical and administrative duties
Ensures a smooth operation within university bureaucracy	Keeps RESILIENCE TNA Coordinator? informed of progress

Please list below the name and contact details of the TNA Coordinator and TNA Contact Person:

TNA Coordinator: [Name]

TNA Contact Person (if different to Coordinator): : [Name]

2. Agree to a minimum number of TNA recipients per academic year: [x].
3. Review and accept TNA applications for your institution, using the TNA Review Criteria.
4. Ensure the provision of a comfortable workspace for each TNA recipient
5. Match TNA recipients with at minimum one onsite scholar or expert.
6. Report to RESILIENCE on the performance of the TNA program and help to develop and improve the TNA program and its procedures.
7. Participate in promoting RESILIENCE TNA, TNA Scholars, and TNA research results, through internal and external communication channels.
8. Permit RESILIENCE to publish a description of your physical and digital collections on your TNA Host webpage as a part of the RESILIENCE website.
9. [additional specific services offered by TNA Host]
10. [additional specific services offered by TNA Host]

Commitments of RESILIENCE

1. RESILIENCE offers access to the RESILIENCE PR and communication channels for recognition and dissemination of the TNA HOST unique collections
2. RESILIENCE offers access to a top-level network of researchers and institutions related to the study of religions.
3. RESILIENCE offers access to a growing set of services and tools tailored to research within your fields of expertise.
4. RESILIENCE is responsible for organising and disseminating each TNA Call for Fellowships.
5. RESILIENCE undertakes to grow the TNA Host network.
6. RESILIENCE monitors the quality of the TNA programme as a whole via targeted evaluation processes.
7. RESILIENCE is responsible for keeping all TNA Hosts up to date on all relevant news and updates concerning the programme and the life of the RI in general.

Additional benefits for the TNA Host institution:

Participating in this Programme also provides TNA HOST with the following additional benefits:

1. Join a unique European research infrastructure for the study of religions.
2. Attract and boost interaction with TNA HOST physical and virtual collections by top-level researchers.
3. Foster peer-reviewed publications specific to TNA HOST collections.
4. Access a network of high-ranking institutions with unique and valuable collections related to research on religions.
5. Participate in an international exchange network of researchers, scholars, archivists, librarians, stakeholders, and policy makers.

RESILIENCE understands that not all institutions can provide the same resources. Therefore, the RI has outlined the minimum commitment which will ensure excellence and hospitality. If there are any additional services available at the TNA HOST have not been included in this MoU, but become available over time, agrees to communicate about them with RESILIENCE in due time.

Final Statement

With this MOU, the TNA HOST joins the RESILIENCE TNA Programme as a TNA host for the duration of the next two academic years: [dates]. After that date, the MOU is subject to renegotiation. Any and all contributions of all parties are in-kind. No financial compensation is offered by or to either party for the duration of this MOU.

This Memorandum of Understanding is the complete agreement between RESILIENCE and the TNA HOST and may be amended only by written agreement signed by each of the parties involved. Signatories must be officially authorised to sign on behalf of the parties and include title and party's name.

Signed,

[TNA Host]

[Date, location]

[Name]

[Role at institution]

[RESILIENCE TNA Coordinator]

[Date, location]

[Name]

[Role at institution]

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9.2 Appendix 2:
Outputs and Outcomes of the TNA
Fellowships
RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase

As of 20 April 2026, the Transnational Access fellowships have resulted in a substantial number of scholarly outputs and dissemination activities. These include **12 publications**, of which 8 are available in Open Access and 4 are not, **14 additional outputs that are forthcoming**, **20 conference papers and presentations**, **1 award**, and **36 news items** published on the RESILIENCE website and in other media.

9.2.1 Publications

9.2.1.1 Open Access Publications

Babameto, Etleva/Pano, Doriana: The Future Higher Education in Albania in the Digital Era – Challenges and Opportunities, in: Journal of Electrical Systems 20/4s (2024), p. 1809–1820, DOI: [10.52783/jes.2244](https://doi.org/10.52783/jes.2244).

Butėnaitė-Switkiewicz, Joanna/Žemaitaitytė, Irena: The Role of Family Bonds in Nurturing Psychological Resilience in Older Adults: “In the Family, You Will Find the Support and Strength to Endure and Live”, in: The Mediterranean Journal of Clinical Psychology 12/3 (2024); DOI: <https://doi.org/10.13129/2282-1619/mjcp-4457>

Iberico Ruiz, Rolando: The Council of the Peruvian Episcopate: A Historical-Theological Study of the Peruvian Participation at the Second Vatican Council (1959-1965), PhD thesis 2025. <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/handle/20.500.12942/765666>

Kasprzak, Artur Antoni: Kolegialność w służbie synodalności. Ryzyko czy szansa XVI Synodu Biskupów?, in: Studia Bobolanum 33/4 (2022), p. 85–105. DOI: 10.5604/01.3001.0016.1448 / [\(PDF\) Kolegialność w służbie synodalności. Ryzyko czy szansa XVI Synodu Biskupów?](#)

Kasprzak, Artur Antoni: Synodalność w teologii Soboru Watykańskiego II, in: Teologia w Polsce 17, 2 (2023), p. 109–127. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31743/twp.2023.17.2.06>

Kasprzak, Artur Antoni: Le ministère épiscopal synodal et la vision de la réforme continue de l’Église d’après le cardinal Giacomo Lercaro à l’aube du Concile Vatican II, in: Warszawskie Studia Teologiczne 37/2 (2024), p. 88–109, DOI: [10.30439/WST.2024.2.4](https://doi.org/10.30439/WST.2024.2.4)

Núñez Bargaño, Natalia: Recovering the Legacy of the Thought of Catholic Lay Women (1945-62), in: JoMaCC (Journal of Modern and Contemporary Christianity), 2/1 (2023), p. 21–44, DOI: [10.30687/JoMaCC/2785-6046/2023/01/001](https://doi.org/10.30687/JoMaCC/2785-6046/2023/01/001) (e-ISSN 2785-6046).

Puchkova, Sofia: The Womb of Flame: The Pre-Christian Origins of a Greco-Syrian Baptismal Metaphor. EUSEBIUS PRIZE ESSAY, in: The Journal of Ecclesiastical History (2025), pp. 1 - 20; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022046925000077>

9.2.1.2 Publications Not Available in Open Access

Anello, Giancarlo: *Persone capitali. Storie di entità giuridiche*, Bologna 2024 [<https://www.marietteditore.it/libro/9788821176883-persone-capitali>].

Butėnaitė-Switkiewicz, Joana: Vyresnio amžiaus asmenų psichologinis atsparumas: rekomendacijos tyrėjams, specialistams, dirbantiems su vyresnio amžiaus asmenimis, ir socialinės politikos formuotojams. Vilnius: Mykolo Romerio universitetas 2024. [VYRESNIO AMŽIAUS ASMENŲ PSICHOLOGINIS ATSPARUMAS: REKOMENDACIJOS TYRĖJAMS, SPECIALISTAMS, DIRBANTIEMS SU VYRESNIO AMŽIAUS ASMENIMIS, IR SOCIALINĖS POLITIKOS FORMUOTOJAMS](#)

Musch, Sebastian: Judaism and Buddhism, in: Oxford Bibliographies in Jewish Studies, ed. Naomi Seidman, New York 2023 (peer reviewed), DOI: 10.1093/OBO/9780199840731-0235 <https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/display/document/obo-9780199840731/obo-9780199840731-0235.xml>

Musch, Sebastian: Christianity and Hinduism: German Views in the Long 19th Century, in: The Routledge Handbook of Christianity and Culture, ed. Yaakov Ariel, Gregor Thuswaldner, and Jens Zimmermann, London 2024, p. 415-427. DOI: 10.4324/9780429260490 https://www.routledge.com/The-Routledge-Handbook-of-Christianity-and-Culture/Ariel-Thuswaldner-Zimmermann/p/book/9780367202590?srsId=AfmBOoFx-XLpVr_68yyO3H8DmduWQRDnnMjytGZlbtzRSUIbFubfQcy

9.2.1.3 Forthcoming Publications

Erquiaga Martínez, Cristina: «May it Ring out over Europe!» España y Europa vistas por tres remitentes extranjeros de Unamuno, in: Dewaele, Hélène (coord.): *Unamuno, Nationalismes et cosmopolitisme*, Paris: Éditions L'Harmattan, 2026 [in press].

Gligor, Mihaela: The architecture of Coexistence. Resilience, the Dynamics of Migration, and Identity in Today's Cyprus, in: Transylvanian Review [ISI journal, open access, forthcoming].

Kapanadze, Giorgi: Specificity of Religious Knowledge and its Philosophical Implications, PhD thesis [defended on 27 February 2024 at New Georgian University].

Kiperwasser, Reuven: Tales of the Solomon Cycle in Palea Interpretata 1, in Slavia Meridionalis 26 [in press].

Lazareanu, Venera: ITSERR Impact Analysis Report (IAR) [Forthcoming April 2026].

Moncion, Laura: Portrait of a Fifteenth-century Recluse and Mystic: The Life of the Venerable Pirona, Recluse of the Third Order of St Francis. Under contract after peer review, Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies [Forthcoming].

Musch, Sebastian: Exclusion by Buddhism; The Search for an Abrahamic Triad without Judaism in the Nineteenth Century, in: The "Excluded Third" in the Co-Production of Judaism, Christianity, and Islam, Heyden, Katharina /Scotto, Davide (ed.), Turnhout: Brepols [Forthcoming 2027].

Musch, Sebastian: Challenging the Abrahamic Triad: Buddhism, Antijudaism, and the Global History of Religion, Cambridge Elements „Global Humanities“ Book Series, Cambridge University Press, forthcoming].

Rosenblieh, Émilie: The right to vote. Practices and debates in Church councils, in: The Cambridge History of Rights, vol. 2 : The Middle Ages, Lidia Lanza, Marco Toste (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge university press [to be published].

Rosenblieh, Émilie: [Habilitation thesis on collective decision-making in general councils in the 15th century, completed 2026/2027].

Scapini; Elia/Iezzi, Federico: Lamba: Mamba State Space Model Adapted to Latin Semantic Retrieval, in: IRCDL (Italian Research Conference on Digital Libraries Proceedings) 2026 [forthcoming].

Scapini; Elia/Iezzi, Federico: Θεὸν ἐκ θεοῦ: a Case Study for Semantic Retrieval in Ancient Greek, in: Commentationes Humanarum Litterarum 2026 [forthcoming].

Sciortino, Gabriella: TNA Management Platform, in: D'Avenia, Fabrizio/Braghi, Gianmarco (eds.), Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE (ITSERR). Digital Humanities for the Information Technology transformation in Religious Studies, Palermo University Press, Palermo 2026 [in press].

Titova, Nelia: A comparative study of the concept of God in the Teaching of St Gregory Palamas and A.N. Whitehead's Philosophy, PhD thesis [forthcoming].

9.2.2 Conference Contributions and Scholarly Presentations

Babameto, Etleva: The future of Higher Education in Albania – Challenges and Opportunities, presented at the 6th International Conference on Recent Trends in Multi-Disciplinary Research (ICRTMDR-23) in Istanbul, 10–11 November 2023.

Butėnaitė-Switkiewicz, Joana: Presentation: Od dna smutku do odporności – opowieść starszej osoby z domu pomocy [en. From Rock Bottom to Resilience: The Story of an Older Person from a Nursing Home], 21–23 November 2025 – X Conference of Narrative Psychology (X Konferencja Psychologii Narracyjnej), SWPS University, Poznań, Poland.

Butėnaitė-Switkiewicz, Joana: Presentation: Navigating Life's Storms: A Qualitative Case Study of Resilience in an Older Woman, 25–26 June 2024 – SOCIN'24 (Social Innovations for Transformative Society, ERUA Summit), Mykolas Romeris University, Lithuania.

Butėnaitė-Switkiewicz, Joana: Presentation: Įžvalgos iš gyvenimo audrų: vyresnio amžiaus moters atsparumas [en. Insights from Life's Storms: The Resilience of an Older Woman], 26–27 April 2024 – Lithuanian Congress of Psychologists 2024, Klaipėda University, Lithuania.

Butėnaitė-Switkiewicz, Joana: Presentation: Two Sides of the Same Coin: Psychological Resilience and Happiness in Lithuanian Adults, 27–29 September 2023 – #RESILIENCE 2023: 9th International Symposium on Resilience Research, Mainz, Germany.

Butėnaitė-Switkiewicz, Joana: Presentation: Psichologinis atsparumas ir jo veiksniai reprezentacinėje Lietuvos suaugusiųjų imtyje [Psychological Resilience and Its Factors in a Representative Sample of Lithuanian Adults], 30 April 2023 – 20th Young Scientists Psychologists' Conference "Partnership Leads", University of Vilnius, Lithuania.

- Kapanadze, Giorgi: Religious Epistemology: the Nature and Character of Spiritual Search, presentation at the European Academy of Religion conference on the 20th of May, 2025 in Palermo.
- Medvedeva, Ksenia: "Green parish" and Other Examples of 'Ecological Conversion' in the Orthodox Church in Greece, Presentation at the International Conference "The Religious Roots of Environmental Justice," online, organized by the University of Denver, USA, October 2023.
- Medvedeva, Ksenia: Environmental Initiatives in the Eastern Orthodox Church: Cases of the U.S. and Greece, Presentation at: Annual Conference of the European Association for the Study of Religions, University of Gothenburg, Sweden, August 2024.
- Medvedeva, Ksenia: Ecological Initiatives in Eastern Orthodox Churches, Presentation at The Scientific Community Networking and Young Scholars Event organized by the Polish Academy of Sciences in Warsaw, Poland, June 12, 2024.
- Medvedeva, Ksenia: Religions and the Environment: Methodological Reflection and the Contribution from Social Sciences, Paper at the international workshop held at the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of the Polish Academy of Sciences in Warsaw, Poland, June 2024.
- Medvedeva, Ksenia: Ecological Projects in Eastern Orthodox Churches, Presentation at the National Gathering of Laudato Si Movement Poland - Światowy Ruch Katolików na rzecz Środowiska in Grzybow, Poland, June 2024.
- Medvedeva, Ksenia: Green Orthodoxy: Ecological Conversion of Eastern Orthodox Churches, Open Lecture with a commentary by Marco Castagnetto, University of Turin, at the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of the Polish Academy of Sciences, May 23, 2024.
- Medvedeva, Ksenia: Environmental Activities of the Eastern Orthodox Church in Greece, Presentation at The International Study of Religion in Eastern and Central Europe Association (ISORECEA) conference in Tirana, Albania, April 2024.
- Medvedeva, Ksenia: Green Orthodoxy: Ecological Conversion of Eastern Orthodox Churches (The Case of Greece), Presentation at the Association for the Study of Eastern Christian History and Culture Tenth Biennial Conference at the Ohio State University in Columbus, Ohio, USA, February 2024.

Pfannes, Benjamin: Verborgene Grausamkeiten: Die „Euthanasie“-Verbrechen in Belgien, Presentation at the Research Colloquium “NS-“Euthanasie”, Zwangssterilisation und Eugenik” at the Hadamar Memorial Centre, 10.-12. October 2024.

Rosenblieh, Émilie: The process of collective decision-making in conciliar assemblies in the 15th century, conference at Julie Claustre’s research seminar devoted to “The making of medieval societies, 12th–15th centuries” at Paris-Cité University 3 February 2025.

Rosenblieh, Émilie: The right to vote. Practices and debates in Church councils, Presentation at the launch event for The Cambridge History of Rights, 2000 BCE to 2025 CE, held at the University of Chicago’s John Boyer Center in Paris on 7 November 2025.

Scapini; Elia/Iezzi, Federico: Lamba: Mamba State Space Model Adapted to Latin Semantic Retrieval, presentation at: IRCDL/Italian Research Conference on Digital Libraries, 20 February 20 2026.

Scapini; Elia/Iezzi, Federico: Θεὸν ἐκ θεοῦ: a Case Study for Semantic Retrieval in Ancient Greek, presentation at: LREC/Language Resources and Evaluation Conference, 11-16 May 2026.

9.2.3 Awards

Puchkova, Sofia: Recipient of the Journal of Ecclesiastical History Eusebius Essay Prize 2025. The award was granted for the essay: The Womb of Flame: The Pre-Christian Origins of a Greco-Syrian Baptismal Metaphor. EUSEBIUS PRIZE ESSAY, in: The Journal of Ecclesiastical History (2025), pp. 1 - 20; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022046925000077>. See [Eusebius Essay Prize Winning Articles](#).

9.2.4 Communication and Dissemination Outputs

Anello, Giancarlo: ["Luxury Time": Having Directly Thousands of Books and Resources at Ones Disposal - RESILIENCE](#) (16 March 2023)

Babameto, Etleva: ["A Useful and Impressive In-Field Experience" - RESILIENCE](#) (24 November 2023)

Butėnaitė-Switkiewicz, Joana: Psichologinis atsparumas: Kaip augti gyvenimo iššūkių akivaizdoje? [Psychological Resilience: How to Grow in the Face of Life's Challenges?] Ateitis 2023, November 3 [popular science publication on psychological resilience in Lithuanian magazine].

Butėnaitė-Switkiewicz, Joana: [Happy to Be Where Theology and Psychology Meet and Have an Interdisciplinary Discussion - RESILIENCE](#) (16 June 2023)

Ciccarello, Domenico: [Domenico Ciccarello: "The Value of Both Old and Modern Physical Books will Never be Overestimated" - RESILIENCE](#) (08 October 2025)

Đulović, Šahsen: UNIVERZITET U SARAJEVU I GAZI HUSREV-BEGOVA BIBLIOTEKA DOMAĆINI ISTRAŽIVAČIMA IZ ITALIJE I ŠVICARSKE [UNSA and The Gazy Husrav-beg Library in Sarajevo hosted TNA researchers from Italy and Switzerland], in: Bilten Gazi Husrev-begove biblioteke broj 11.: Gazi Husrev-begova biblioteka u 2025, Sarajevo 2026, p. 53-54. [Gazi Husrev-begova biblioteka u 2025. godini](#) (15 January 2026)

Exalto, John: [A Unique Dive into Comeniology in the Czech Republic - RESILIENCE](#) (03 July 2025)

Ferraro, Gianluca: [Exploring AI and the Study of Religion - RESILIENCE](#) (10 September 2025)

Forestier, Luc: Interview: [Luc Forestier's RESILIENCE TNA Research Stay 2025 - YouTube](#)

Gligor, Mihaela: [Εξερευνώντας την ταυτότητα και την ανθεκτικότητα στην Κύπρο – Η έρευνα της Δρ Mihaela Gligor στην Αγία Νάπα – Famagusta News](#) [Exploring Identity and Resilience in Cyprus – Dr. Mihaela Gligor's Research in Agia Napa] (19 December 2025)

Hoffmann, Lennard: [Fragments of Faith and Memory: Researching Sacred Heritage at the Comenius Museum - RESILIENCE](#) (10 November 2025)

Kapanadze, Giorgi: [Indispensable Infrastructure for Present and Future Generations of Scholars - RESILIENCE](#) (13 May 2024)

Kapanadze, Giorgi: [Interview with Giorgi Kapanadze on the benefits of a Transnational Access fellowship - YouTube](#)

Kasprzak, Artur: [Working for the Second Vatican Council and Humanity, so that We May be More United - RESILIENCE](#) (05 January 2023)

- Kasprzak, Artur: Interview about his RESILIENCE TNA research stay in January 2023: [Artur Kasprzak RESILIENCE TNA Jan 2023 - YouTube](#)
- Kiperwasser, Reuven: [Broadening Horizons with Transnational Access - RESILIENCE](#) (23 September 2024)
- John Amos Comenius Museum, Host for the RESILIENCE Transnational Access (TNA) Fellowship Programme: Presentation of the TNA Host Institution: [John Amos Comenius Museum, Host for the RESILIENCE Transnational Access \(TNA\) Fellowship Programme](#)
- Lazareanu, Venera: [Bridging Impact: A Transnational Access Experience in Sarajevo - RESILIENCE](#) (11 August 2025)
- Losada, José Manuel: [A Unique Experience for José Manuel Losada - RESILIENCE](#) (30 March 2023)
- Medvedeva, Ksenia: [Ksenia Medvedeva: "It turns my visit into a comprehensive experience of Greek Orthodoxy" - RESILIENCE](#) (20 December 2022)
- mikado Library in Aachen, Presentation: [mikado Library in Aachen, Germany, a Host Institution for RESILIENCE Transnational Access \(TNA\) - YouTube](#)
- Nnabugwu, Chidiebere: [Chidiebere Nnabugwu: "Indeed, it felt like home." - RESILIENCE](#) (19 September 2022)
- Ostapczuk, Jerzy: ["Travel to the Past with the Help of our Friends" - RESILIENCE](#) (23 September 2022)
- Papasidero, Marco: [Travelling to Brussels to Further Develop an AI Tool in Palermo - RESILIENCE](#) (24 June 2025)
- Puchkova, Sofia: [Sofia Puchkova: Productive TNA Stay, Full of Discoveries - RESILIENCE](#) (21 February 2023)
- Puchkova, Sofia: [Prestigious Eusebius Essay Prize goes to TNA Scholar Sofia Puchkova - RESILIENCE](#) (14 May 2025)
- RESILIENCE/ITSERR: [Attractive Conditions TNA Fellowship at ITSERR Consortium Partners - RESILIENCE](#) (19 October 2024)
- RESILIENCE/TNA Hosts: Introduction of the RESILIENCE TNA Programme: [RESILIENCE TNA Video 01 00 June 2022 - YouTube](#) (June 2022)

- Rosenblieh, Émilie: [Émilie Rosenblieh: Direct Access to All Editions of Conciliar Sources - RESILIENCE](#) (27 February 2024)
- Scapini, Elia: [From Ancient Texts to Modern Tools: Elia Scapini's TNA Fellowship at KU Leuven - RESILIENCE](#) (16 October 2025)
- Steiner, Martin: [Research Through Encounters: Tracing a Life Lost in Srebrenica - RESILIENCE](#) (20 December 2025)
- Stevanović, Sanja: ["Unified Efforts Can Surmount Any Research Obstacle" - RESILIENCE](#) (28 November 2023)
- Titova, Nelia: [This Research Centre Really Makes a Difference - RESILIENCE](#) (02 August 2023)
- Titova, Nelia: Interview on the RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship at the Volos Academy for Theological Studies – [Nelia Titova RESILIENCE TNA Research Stay 2023](#) (02 August 2023)
- Titova, Nelia: Slideshow on the RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship at the Volos Academy for Theological Studies – [Nelia Titova RESILIENCE TNA Experiences 2023](#) (02 August 2023)
- Vepřek, Miroslav: [Miroslav Vepřek: 3 Reasons Why Doing Research in a Library Abroad is Important - RESILIENCE](#) (13 March 2025)

10 Applicable Documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
A1	28/08/2022	Grant Agreement 101079792

11 Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
R1	28/11/2025	D2.2: User Services Catalogue 02.00: RESILIENCE_WP2_D2.2_UserServicesCatalogue_02.00_FINAL.pdf
R2	30/10/2025	D2.5: TNA Services Management Plan: RESILIENCE_WP2_D2.5_TNAServicesManagementPlan_FINAL.pdf
R3	21/11/2024	D4.2: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan RESILIENCE PPP, 2nd version: RESILIENCE_WP4_D4.2_CDEP_01.00_FINAL.pdf
R4	19/01/2026	D4.3: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan RESILIENCE PPP, looking forward: RESILIENCE_WP4_CDEP_D4.3_01.00_FINAL.pdf
R5	19/01/2026	RESILIENCE Report WP4 Statistics M1-M41 (Confidential Appendix to D4.3)
R6	30/12/2025	RESILIENCE WP4 TNA Communication Workflow, FINAL 02.00 (Confidential)
R7	02/10/2023	RESILIENCE_WP2_TNA_Strategy_2023-2026 (Confidential Report)

12 Revision Log

ID	Date	Nature of Revision	Approved by
[R1]	[DD/MM/YYYY]		
[R2]			
[R3]			

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